

A review of storms and marine coastal flooding in the Baltic Sea – Insights from instrumental, historical and sedimentary record

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Marine coastal flooding
Coastal hazards
Coastal disasters
Storm deposits
Storminess
Historical archives
Holocene

ABSTRACT

This paper reviews the state of knowledge on past and present storms and marine coastal flooding (MCF) events of various origins within the Baltic Sea, which is an economically and environmentally important part of northwestern Europe. We show that the combination of sedimentary, historical and instrumental records provides the most comprehensive insight into the history of storms and MCF. The frequency and intensity of these events vary considerably throughout the region and over the time (past 7000 years). The southwestern and southern Baltic Sea coasts are identified as the area most vulnerable to hazard posed by storms and MCF, both in the past and in the future. The best records of storms come from urbanized areas where long tide-gauge and historical records are available, while storminess history is best reconstructed from inland sedimentary and peat archives. Archives of MCF have been preserved only in a few locations and represent local, but temporally comprehensive record of the most severe events. However, it remains challenging to relate records of storms, storminess, and storm-induced MCF to each other.

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1. Introduction

The magnitude and frequency of climate-driven storms and marine coastal flooding (MCF) events of various origin may increase due to rapidly changing climate (e.g.: [Bevacqua et al., 2020](#); [Almar et al., 2021](#)). In addition rising sea-level (e.g.: [Taherkhani et al., 2020](#); [Magnan et al., 2022](#)) further exacerbates these hazards. This poses an inevitable threat to coastal communities on a global scale, and the coastal zone of the Baltic Sea, an economically and environmentally important part of northern and central Europe, is not unique in this respect. The southern Baltic Sea coast has been identified as the “hot-spot” where the frequency of storm-induced MCF overtopping coastal barriers has been one of the highest in the world during recent decades and is expected to rise in the future ([Almar et al., 2021](#); [Meier et al., 2022](#)).

In the light of the economic and societal importance of the Baltic Sea and the ongoing environmental changes, it is essential to review the state of knowledge on coastal hazards including storms and MCF of various origins. As revealed by worldwide studies the understanding of the past of these hazards is particularly important, as it provides insights into (i) the long-term recurrence period and in the case of climate driven processes, also changes in the frequency and magnitude of events over time ([Chaumillon et al., 2017](#); [Muller et al., 2017](#); [Oliva et al., 2018](#); [Engel et al., 2020](#); [Minamidate and Goto, 2024](#)), (ii) the response of coastal systems to storms and extreme MCF events ([Woodroffe and Murray-Wallace, 2012](#); [Leszczyńska et al., 2022](#)), and (iii) the presence of low-frequency and often high-magnitude coastal flooding hazards like tsunamis ([Jankaew et al., 2008](#); [Goto et al., 2011](#)). All of these are very important for coastal planning, risk reduction, and mitigation strategies ([Goto et al., 2014](#); [Ramm et al., 2018](#); [Toimil et al., 2020](#)). Based on insights from the past and present, it is possible to infer what kind of impacts are expected for various types of coast in the future.

The aim of this paper is to systematically review the knowledge on past storms and MCF in the Baltic Sea region ([Fig. 1](#)) as well as the

advantages and limitations of various research approaches dedicated to different timescales. Sedimentary and historical archives, as well as instrumental records were taken into consideration. The specific objectives of this review are: i) to analyse geographical and topical distribution of the research on storms and MCF (section 3); ii) to present the state of the research and knowledge on their frequency and magnitude (section 4); iii) to review and discuss the applied research methods for various timescales and coastal settings (section 5); iv) to attempt deciphering the impact of storms and MCF events on coastal settings (section 6); and v) to discuss their observed and predicted impact in relation to the ongoing climate change (section 7) and the resulting challenges for the future (section 8). For the purposes of this review, we attempt to distinguish between the research on i) storms and ii) storm-induced MCF events, and only briefly discuss flooding events of other origins, such as seiches, meteotsunamis and tsunamis. The review focuses on the last ca. 7000 years following the Littorina transgression ([Björck, 1995](#); [Andrén et al., 2011](#); [Rosentau et al., 2017, 2021](#); [Stattegger and Leszczyńska, 2023](#)). The storm and MCF events are divided into three groups: i) those which occurred before the 14th century CE and are documented only in sedimentary archives, ii) those from the period from the 14th century to 1872 CE documented also in historical records, and iii) those which occurred after 1872 CE and are additionally documented by instrumental monitoring.

1.1. Storms, storminess, storm surge, and marine coastal flooding (MCF) – Definitions

The terms *storm*, *storminess*, *storm surge* and *marine coastal flooding* (MCF) used throughout this paper do not have consistent definitions in the research literature. Here, we present an overview of commonly used definitions and refer to the definitions used in this paper ([Table 1](#)). According to the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), a storm is a severe weather condition characterised by high wind speeds. It is

Fig. 1. Coastal types around the Baltic Sea. Discrete coastal types are differentiated with coloured lines (modified from Lampe, 1995) – see the key on the map. Black line separates zones of various isostatic rebound and morphodynamic (based on Harff et al., 2017). Numbers denote the most important cities mentioned in the text and their names are given in the key on the map. Insets: A. Baltic Sea in Europe. Basemap source: DEM – HELCOM Metadata Catalogue, 2005-07-01; bathymetry – HELCOM Metadata Catalogue - 2013-11-15; coastline – HELCOM Metadata Catalogue - 2018-01-31; countries – HELCOM Metadata Catalogue - 2017-12-05.

classified using the Beaufort scale (Bft), which is widely used to measure storm intensity (Fischer-Bruns et al., 2005). The empirical Beaufort scale correlates wind force with observable conditions, both offshore and on land, defining specific wind speeds range in km/h, m/s, mph or knots. In Beaufort scale a “storm” is defined as wind speed exceeding force 9 Bft (>89 km/h) (Fischer-Bruns et al., 2005). The storm intensity is also defined as the 98th percentile of daily maximum wind speed at a height of 10 m above the ground or sea surface (Pinto et al., 2007; Mölter et al., 2016). However, in this review, we adopt a modified definition based on

Morton et al. (2007), which describes a storm as the result of sea-atmosphere coupling, leading to strong winds, raised water levels, storm surge and destructive waves. This generalized definition does not specify fixed thresholds for wind speed, water level, or wave-height, as the review encompasses research papers using varying criteria to define storm conditions. Moreover, winds weaker than widely accepted thresholds cited above also play a significant role in coastal morphodynamics.

The term “storminess” is inherently associated with storms. In the

Table 1
Definitions of terms used in the paper.

Phenomenon	Definitions as used in the current paper	Based on
storm	the result of sea-atmosphere coupling, leading to strong winds, raised water levels, storm surge and destructive waves	Fischer-Bruns et al. (2005) Pinto et al. (2007) Möller et al. (2016) Morton (2007)
storminess	frequency of storms, in a given timespan, which depends on the timescale of the research	Fischer-Bruns et al. (2005) Pinto et al. (2007)
storm surge	significant rise in sea-level caused by storm conditions, without reference to a specific national definitions	Gönnert et al. (2001) Schwartz (2005) International glossary of hydrology, (1992)
marine coastal flooding (MCF)	the inundation by marine waters of coastal areas encompassing beaches, backbarrier regions and urbanized shorelines without being restricted to a specific distance from the coast	Piotrowski et al. (2017) Pelikka et al. (2014, 2020) Bendixen et al. (2013)

North Atlantic region, storminess is usually defined as the number of days per year with daily near-surface maximum wind speed reaching or exceeding 9 Bft (Fischer-Bruns et al., 2005). In contrast, Pinto et al. (2007) quantify storminess by analyzing the annual number of days per year when local wind speeds exceed the 98th percentile of days per year maximum wind speed at a height of 10 m. Another approach was proposed by Schmith et al. (1998). They define storminess based on monthly mean pressure changes over periods of 1000, 200 and 20 h. In the Baltic Sea region, storminess is usually described by the frequency

and intensity of deep low-pressure centers, defined as those with a central pressure of 960 hPa or lower, or when the pressure difference between the center and the periphery reaches 70–80 hPa. These characteristics are analysed over specific defined timeframes, such as months, years, or decades (Rutgersson et al., 2015). In this review, storminess refers to the frequency of storms in a given time-span, which depends on the timescale of the research (Table 1).

A “storm surge” is defined as an increase in sea-level above the normal, i.e. tidal corrected level near the coast, lasting from several minutes to several days (Gönnert et al., 2001). It is generated by a passing storm (Schwartz, 2005) or low-pressure centre (International Glossary of Hydrology, 1992). In the Baltic Sea, storm surge measurements do not require tidal adjustment as the tidal amplitudes do not exceed 0.2 m (Medvedev and Kulikov, 2019). Storm surges are measured based on tide-gauge readings with 200 active tide-gauges monitoring sea-level across the Baltic Sea (Copernicus Marine Service, as accessed in May 2024 - www.marineinsitu.eu). National institutions, conducting independent hydrometeorological monitoring, issue warnings for high, dangerously high and critical water levels (Fig. 2). The threshold for critical water level ranges from 0.5 to 2.5 m along the Baltic Sea coast, depending on the country. This results from various approaches to model storm-induced water level rise applied by individual countries, tide-gauge locations, bathymetry, coastal geomorphology, exposure to prevailing winds directions and hydrotechnical infrastructure. In addition, each Baltic Sea country has its own system for defining marine coastal flooding hazard (Fig. 2). In Lithuania, a single critical water level defines flood conditions (Lithuanian Hydrometeorological Service, 2024). In Poland and Sweden, there are two levels: warning and direct high risk of flooding (Institute of Meteorology and Water Management,

Fig. 2. Classification of water levels at the coast that are classified as ‘critical’ (in the context of hydrological warnings) in the countries around the Baltic Sea. * denotes the maximum value range from – to, in m above zero of the local tide-gauge (mean sea-level), which depends on the site. Yellow, orange and red colour denotes different levels of warning, with red being the most serious. Sources: Denmark – Danish Meteorological Institute, Stormflodsvarsling, 2024; Germany - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie, Wasserstandsvorhersage an der Ostsee, 2024; Poland – Institute of Meteorology and Water Management, Hydro 2024; Lithuania - Lietuvos Respublikos Aplinkos Ministro 2024; Latvia – Latvian Environment, Geology and Meteorology Centre, Brīdinājumi, 2024; Estonia – Hoiatuste kriteeriumid, 2024a Environment Agency, Hoiatuste kriteeriumid, 2024; Finland – Finnish Meteorological Institute, Meriveden korkeusvaroitus, 2024; Sweden – Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute, Varningsdefinitioner, 2024 and Schöld et al., 2017. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

2024; Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute, 2024). Denmark also employs a warning and critical water level system, but the latter is calculated individually for each port on a case-by-case basis (Danish Meteorological Institute, 2024). Institutions in Germany, Finland, Estonia and Latvia follow a three-level warning system, the third of which is the critical alarm level. Due to varied definitions of the storm surge around the Baltic Sea, this review adopts generalised approach. Here, the term “storm surge” refers to significant rise in sea-level caused by storm conditions, without reference to specific national definitions.

Currently, as a result of the Baltic Sea Hydrographic Commission project, sea-level measurements in the countries bordering the Baltic Sea are being unified to one common reference level, the Baltic Sea Chart Datum 2000 (BSCD2000). The zero level of BSCD2000 aligns with the Normal Amsterdams Peil (NAP) within the European Vertical Reference System (EVRS). All countries that previously used the Kronstadt reference system, except the Russian Federation, have either switched to EVRS or are in process of doing so (Schwabe et al., 2020). This unification facilitates the regional comparisons, and improves the accessibility of sea-level information across the Baltic region.

“Marine coastal flooding” (MCF) is defined as the inundation by marine waters of coastal areas encompassing beaches, backbarrier regions, and urbanized shorelines, without being restricted to a specific distance from the coast. MCF events may arise from a range of processes, including storms, meteotsunamis, tsunamis, infragravity waves and seiches. Meteotsunami, is an event of coastal flooding caused by a long sea wave generated by rapid (within tens of minutes) and significant (several tens of hPa) changes in atmospheric pressure over the sea. Meteotsunamis are triggered by pressure disturbances associated with weather fronts, thunderstorms, cyclones, or atmospheric gravity waves (Monserrat et al., 2006; Pelliikka et al., 2020). Meteotsunamis tend to amplify in shallow water and can cause coastal flooding that reaches several meters above sea-level (Monserrat et al., 2006). Other MCF event type discussed on many occasions, both in peer-reviewed journals and outside is tsunami. Tsunami is long oceanic wave typically triggered by underwater earthquakes, subaerial or submarine landslides, or asteroid impacts (International Oceanographic Commission, 2019). The seiche is the distortion of the water surface caused by the standing waves with long period of water oscillation (usually longer than 3 h) generating the largest vertical oscillations at each end of a body of water. Seiches are caused by pressure changes associated with mesoscale, deep low-pressure centres moving across the Baltic Sea.

The causes of MCF can often be identified through instrumental and historical timeframe. However in the geological time perspective, its precise origin frequently remains uncertain and multiple proxy approach has to be employed (e.g. Kortekaas and Dawson, 2007; Morton et al., 2007; Phantuwongraj and Choowong, 2012; Donnelly et al., 2017). Due to this ambiguity, researchers have adopted various non-genetic, descriptive terms such as catastrophic saltwater inundation (Chagué-Goff and Goff, 1999), extreme coastal events (Pleskot et al., 2023), and extreme waves (Engel et al., 2020). Here, we use the general term MCF (Table 1) to encompass all of these and to reflect various high-energy marine incursions in coastal environments, which can leave a sedimentary record.

1.2. The Baltic Sea setting

The Baltic Sea (Fig. 1) is a large brackish water body of 415,266 km² including the Belt Sea/Kattegat with an average salinity of 7.4 PSU (Emeis et al., 2003), and negligible tidal amplitudes (Medvedev and Kulikov, 2019). It is a marginal sea, connected to the North Sea through the Danish Straits, extending from 54° to 66°N and 10° to 30°E (Harff et al., 2017). The Baltic Sea has an average depth of 50–53 m, with a maximum depth of 459 m (Jakobsson et al., 2019). It is characterised by strong salinity decrease from Danish Straits to Bothnian Gulf and significant water stratification, driven by the density contrast between the

saline bottom water and the fresher surface layer (Harff et al., 2017). Due to its predominant meridional extent and the presence of large bays, such as the Bothnian Bay, Gulf of Finland, and Gulf of Riga, the Baltic Sea exhibits strong environmental gradients shaped by both natural processes and human activities along its coasts. The Baltic Sea drainage area spans 1.729 × 10⁶ km² and is currently populated by approximately 85 million people (HELCOM, 2021, as accessed in June 2024: <https://helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/>). The most densely populated areas, with biggest cities and ports concentrate along the coasts of southwestern Sweden (Stockholm, Malmö), eastern Denmark (Copenhagen), northeastern Germany (Kiel, Lübeck, Rostock), northern Poland (Gdańsk, Gdynia, Szczecin-Świnoujście), western Lithuania (Klaipėda) and Latvia (Riga) and Gulf of Finland (Tallin, Helsinki, Hamina-Kotka, St. Petersburg) (HELCOM, 2021; Liviņa et al., 2016; Synak-Miłosz and Rozmarynowska-Mrozek, 2023).

1.2.1. The geology and palaeogeography

There are two main factors controlling the susceptibility of the coast to erosion, including the one caused by storms and MCF events. These are i) the relative glacioisostatic movement of the area where the shoreline is located and ii) the geology and local topography/geomorphology. Geologically, the northern Baltic Sea extends across the Precambrian Baltic Shield and its southern part lies within the East European Platform. The Precambrian basement of the East European Platform is mainly covered by Paleozoic sedimentary rocks. The southwestern margin of the Baltic Sea belongs to the Paleozoic and Mesozoic West European Platform, which is separated from the East European Platform by the Teisseyre-Tornquist Zone (Uścińowicz, Sz., 2014).

The region now occupied by the Baltic Sea has functioned as a sedimentary basin multiple times throughout geological history (Šliaupa and Hoth, 2011; Andrén et al., 2011), the formation of the modern Baltic Sea started with the Scandinavian Ice Sheet retreat, ca. 17,000 calibrated years Before Present (cal. years BP) in the southwest and before 10,000 cal. years BP in the north (Andrén et al., 2011). Its evolution was primarily driven by glacioisostatic rebound and eustatic sea-level changes, leading to alternating its lacustrine, brackish, and marine phases during the stages of Baltic Ice Lake, Yoldia Sea and Ancylus Lake until the Littorina transgression. Between 8600 and 8000 cal. years BP, along with rapid sea-level rise, a permanent connection to the North Atlantic was established via the Danish Straits (Andrén et al., 2011; Stattegger and Leszczyńska, 2023). The Littorina transgression gradually slowed, stabilizing around 7000 cal. years BP when sea-level was between 5 and 4 m below the present day sea-level (Lampe et al., 2011; Lampe and Lampe, 2021; Sydor and Uścińowicz, 2023), setting the time limits of the evolution of the Baltic Sea in its present shape.

Since the end of the Littorina transgression, the palaeogeographical evolution of the Baltic Sea continued to be controlled by eustatic sea-level rise and glacioisostatic movements: uplift in the north and slight subsidence in the south (Lampe et al., 2011; Harff et al., 2017; Lampe and Lampe, 2021; Rosentau et al., 2021, 2023; Sydor and Uścińowicz, 2023). In the northern part of the Baltic Sea, along the coasts of Sweden (from Scania to Stockholm), Latvia, Estonia, Russia and southern parts of Finland, isostatic uplift has exceeded the eustatic rise of sea-level, resulting in a permanent regression of the sea and progradational character of the coast (e.g. Berglund, 2004; Lindén et al., 2006; Rosentau et al., 2017, 2023). At present the relative sea-level in Bothnian Bay is dropping at rates of up to 8 mm/year compensating the acceleration in global sea-level rise (PSMSL Data Explorer, 2024). On the contrary, along the southern Baltic Sea coast of Denmark, Germany, Poland and Lithuania, since the Littorina transgression, the sea-level has continued to rise, reaching the present level resulting in retrogradational coast. Throughout the instrumental record timeframe, the rate of eustatic sea-level rise reached from 0.8 to 3 mm/year, reflecting the acceleration in global sea-level rise, and long-term isostatic subsidence (Kowalczyk, 2019; Kelln et al., 2022; WMO, 2023). In the southern part of the Baltic Sea, there are no indicators for the sea-level higher than that at present

(Bennike and Jensen, 1998, 2011; Lampe et al., 2005, 2011; Uścińowicz, Sz., 2003; 2006; Lampe and Lampe, 2021; Uścińowicz, Sz., et al., 2022; Szydor and Uścińowicz, 2022, 2024).

1.2.2. Baltic coast types

In the area of rebound, coasts are prograding and in the area of subsidence, shorelines are retrograding. The Baltic Sea coastline may therefore be divided into three regions based on the major processes affecting the morphogenesis: i) the region of prograding coast; ii) the region where the interplay of progradation of the coast and wave-driven morphodynamics shape the shoreline and iii) the area where wave- and aeolian-driven morphodynamics coexists with retrograding shorelines (Fig. 1).

There have been several attempts to classify the coastal settings around the Baltic Sea based on their geology and geomorphology (Łomniewski et al., 1975; Gudelis, 1967; Lampe, 2005; Håkanson, 2014; Labuz, 2015). To illustrate the influence of storms and MCF on the evolution of the shorelines in the current review we use the genetic classification of the coastal types based on Lampe (1995). We modify the original classification merging genetically similar types of the coasts based on their susceptibility to storms and MCF influence (Fig. 1). Coasts are divided into three major types: (i) erodible unconsolidated sedimentary coast, (ii) erodible consolidated sedimentary coast, and (iii) resistant rock coast. The proposed classification on the background of the direction of isostatic movement of a given stretch of a shoreline allowed to characterize the susceptibility of the coasts to erosion.

The erodible unconsolidated sedimentary coast (type i) primarily consist of low-lying topography, flat sandy coasts such as sandy spits and barriers, deltas and dunes, which may include meadows, wetlands, lagoons and lakes in the back-barrier area. The contemporary intense erosion of this type of coast along the Baltic Sea is caused by extreme consecutive storms and storm-induced MCF, particularly in the absence of sufficient protective sea-ice during winter storms. Another important factor contributing to the degradation of these erodible unconsolidated sedimentary coast is a decline in sediment supply (Deng et al., 2017). Each MCF event reshapes the geomorphology of the coast and transports a portion of sediment inland (Moskalewicz et al., 2024). Coasts of type (i) are present along most of the southwestern, southern and southeastern retrograding coast. They create continuous stretches along the German, Polish, Lithuanian, Latvian and within Gulf of Finland along Estonian and Russian coasts. Small stretches of this coast type also occur along the prograding coast, along northern Denmark and southern Sweden (Fig. 1).

Erodible consolidated sedimentary coasts (type ii) form cliffs mainly in clastic deposits of Palaeogene and Neogene sediments as well as Late Cretaceous chalk and Paleozoic (Devonian) sandstone. They are highly vulnerable to erosion caused by wave action during storms and storm surges, especially when facilitated by rainfall and freeze-thaw cycles. They occupy stretches of the progradational coast in Sweden, Denmark as well as retrogradational coast in Germany and Poland. Some cliffs made of chalk, limestone and sandstone, more susceptible to erosion, occur in Germany, Denmark, Latvia (Gulf of Riga) along retrogradational coasts as well as Estonia and Finland along progradational coasts (Gulf of Finland) (Fig. 1).

The resistant rock coasts (type iii) within the Baltic Sea consist of hard rock cliffs, skerries, fjords and fjärds. These coasts are resistant to erosion. They primarily occupy the western and northern stretches of the Baltic Sea shoreline, along the Finnish coasts of the Bothnian Bay and Gulf of Finland as well as Swedish coasts of the open Baltic and Bothnian Bay (Fig. 1) with progradational coasts.

1.3. Climatic setting of the Baltic Sea

1.3.1. Holocene evolution of the climate within the Baltic Sea region

The Baltic Sea region, due to its vast geographical extent, spans two climatic zones: a humid, subpolar climate in the north and northeast and

an oceanic, temperate climate in the south and southwest. Its climate evolved to its present condition after the last deglaciation under the main influence of orbital forcing, but also chaotic interactions between discrete components of the system, including the recent anthropogenic influence (Meier et al., 2022). After the decay of the Fennoscandian ice-sheet, the gradual amelioration of climate was interrupted by a short-lived cooling event around 8200 cal. years BP. After this event, a steady warming trend ensued, culminating in the Holocene Thermal Maximum (HTM) at around 6000 cal. years BP (Meier et al., 2022). During the HTM, winter temperatures across the Baltic Sea region were ca. 3 °C higher than those recorded at the end of pre-industrial times. Around 4000 cal. years BP, a prolonged millennial-scale cooling phase began, lasting until the 10th century CE. Between the 10th and the 14th centuries CE temperatures were relatively stable, reaching levels approximately 0.5 °C higher than those of the early 19th century CE, prior to the Industrial Revolution in the 1850s. The recent 500 years within the Baltic Sea region have been characterised by small scale, rapid climate shifts, centennial-scale variability and strengthening of decadal and interannual climate variability. Particularly cold periods occurred in the late 16th century CE (beginning of the Little Ice Age), the first half of the 17th century CE, and the early 18th century CE. Over the past 150 years temperature changes in the Baltic Sea region can be divided into three phases: warming until the 1930s, a slight cooling until the 1960s, and continuously accelerating warming since then (Von Storch et al., 2015). Due to the significant meridional extent of the Baltic Sea climatic changes did not take place with the same intensity in its northern and southern regions. For instance, between 1970 and 2008 the highest increase in temperature took place in the Gulf of Bothnia (around 0.5–0.6 °C per decade) during autumn and winter. In contrast, the smallest temperature increase was observed in the central and southern part of the Baltic Sea (about 0.2–0.3 °C per decade) during spring and summer. The precipitation pattern also changed regionally – in the northern Baltic Sea the precipitation decreased, while in the southern part it increased. However, the risk of extreme precipitation events has risen during the 20th century throughout the whole Baltic Sea. Similarly, the length of the winter season has decreased within the whole region (Von Storch et al., 2015).

1.3.2. Present day climate and storm weather scenarios

Currently, the weather within the Baltic Sea region is shaped by the regional atmospheric circulation patterns (Rutgersson et al., 2022; Meier et al., 2022) associated with the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and circulation patterns related to the Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation (AMO). The NAO (Hurrell et al., 2003) is defined by the pressure difference between the Azores High and the Icelandic Low (Wanner et al., 2001; Hurrell et al., 2003) and is expressed by the NAO index. The phase and strength of NAO reflect the position of Atlantic Westerly Jet that drives air masses, in particular mesoscale low-pressure centres, are particularly important for storm weather development. Positive NAO phases are in the area of the Baltic Sea associated with mild temperatures, increased precipitation, westerly winds and enhanced storminess. Negative NAO phases come with a weaker than usual difference in pressure, southward shift of westerly winds, more frequent easterly winds and are characterised by warm summers, cold winters, and less precipitation (Hurrell et al., 2003). The most recent research (Scott et al., 2021; Masselink et al., 2023) indicates a strong correlation in phasing of NAO with extra regional circulation pattern of Western Europe Pressure Anomaly.

Currently, there are three main storm weather scenarios causing the most severe storms within the Baltic Sea region (Fig. 3). All of them are associated with the cold season of the year (autumn and winter). The lack of extensive summer storms is associated with the absence of deep low pressure centres in the region within the warm part of the year (cyclogenesis is weakest in summer because thermal contrasts between oceans and land are smallest). In the first storm weather scenario (i), the mesoscale low-pressure centers travel across the sea from the west-

Fig. 3. Weather setups that are known to cause severe storms within the Baltic Sea region. A. A low-pressure centers travel across the sea from the west-south-west to the north-north-east trajectory, causing storms with westerly winds mainly in the eastern Baltic Sea. B. A low-pressure centres move from the north-north-west to the south or from the north-west to the east resulting in northeasterly winds and severe storm conditions in the S and SW Baltic Sea. C. A low pressure centres move from the west to the east across Denmark and southern Scandinavia, followed by strong northwesterly wind. See text for further explanation. Basemap source: DEM – HELCOM Metadata Catalogue, 2005-07-01; bathymetry – HELCOM Metadata Catalogue - 2013-11-15; coastline – HELCOM Metadata Catalogue - 2018-01-31; countries – HELCOM Metadata Catalogue - 2017-12-05.

south-west to the north-north-east trajectory, resulting in persistent westerly winds along the eastern coast of the Baltic Sea (Suursaar and Sooäär, 2007; Averkiev and Klevanny, 2010) (Fig. 3a). In the second storm weather scenario (ii), the mesoscale low-pressure centres move from the north-north-west to the south or from the north-west to the east while a high pressure system develops over northern Scandinavia. This configuration causes steep pressure gradient and following strong northeasterly winds (Fig. 3b). The third storm weather scenario (iii) is associated with the low pressure centres moving from the west to the east across Denmark and southern Scandinavia, followed by strong

northwesterly wind (Fig. 3c) (Clemmensen et al., 2016).

1.4. Storm and marine coastal flooding (MCF) hazard

1.4.1. Factors influencing storm and MCF hazard

The susceptibility of a given coast to storm and MCF hazard depends mainly on the interplay of the local coastal type described in section 1.2.2 with storm weather setup described in the section 1.3.2. Other factors influencing the storm and MCF hazard comprise the height of the initial water level at the set up of the storm, the height of the storm

surge, the wave setup and runup, the configuration of the coast and its elevation, in particular the height of the beach barrier as well as the wind strength and direction (Stockdon et al., 2006; Goslin and Clemmensen, 2017).

The initial water level at the set up of a storm may be influenced by the filling rate of the basin with water from the North Atlantic and the North Sea or the presence of seiche (Suursaar et al., 2002; Hünicke et al., 2015). Persistent westerly winds (storm weather scenario i) transport water into the Baltic Sea basin through the Danish straits. The inflow events, most pronounced during the cold season of the year, may result in a general sea-level rise up to 1 m, in particular in the eastern part of the sea (Leppäranta and Myrberg, 2009; Jaagus and Suursaar, 2013; Hünicke et al., 2015). The seiche effect may cause an additional rise of the sea-level at the western coasts (Wolski and Wiśniewski, 2021).

The storm-surge level and the wave setup and runup are inherently associated with the local wind strength, direction and duration before and at the time of the storm event (Wolski and Wiśniewski, 2020). A landward wind, perpendicular to the coastline, if sufficient fetch distance is available, builds up the highest wave setup and runup increasing the hazard of MCF. The configuration of the coast and its elevation, including the presence and the height of a beach barrier, directly influences the extent of the MCF. Within the Baltic Sea the most vulnerable shorelines are those that, together with the barrier, do not exceed approximately 3.3 m above mean sea-level (a.m.s.l.). The latter is based on the maximum measured elevation of the storm surge height of 3.3 m a.m.s.l., including the wave setup and runup during the storm in 1872 (Rosenhagen and Bork, 2009). Within the Baltic Sea, the coastal type most vulnerable to MCF induced by storms is low-lying topography sandy beaches and coastal wetlands.

1.4.2. Regional variability of storm and MCF hazard within the Baltic Sea

The coasts along the eastern Baltic Sea (Gulf of Riga, Gulf of Finland) are particularly vulnerable to extreme storms and MCF events associated with the weather scenario (i) (section 1.3.2) characterised by low pressure centres travelling from west-south-west to north-east-north. In this scenario the persistent westerly wind transports water through the Danish Straits from the North Sea and the filling rate of the Baltic Sea becomes higher (Suursaar et al., 2002; Hünicke et al., 2015). The increased volume of water may raise the sea-level in bays of the eastern sector of up to 250 cm (e.g. Pärnu, Gulf of Riga). This combined with the prevailing low, flat topography of the erodible, unconsolidated sedimentary coasts within this part of the sea, storm wind speeds exceeding 90–100 km/h and resulting storm surge and wave setup causes exceptionally high MCF hazard (Suursaar et al., 2002, 2003).

When the Baltic Sea's water level is high and the deep cyclonic lows change the trajectories from the north-north-west to the south or from the north-west to the east (storm weather scenario ii), causing a change of the major wind from westerly to easterly and northeasterly direction, then the most severe storm conditions occur along the southwesterly coasts of the Baltic Sea, along German (Bay of Mecklenburg, Bay of Kiel) and Danish shoreline facing the Baltic Sea. The susceptibility of these shorelines is additionally increased by the dominant erodible, unconsolidated character of the coast. Prolonged easterly and north-easterly winds push the water from the eastern sectors of the Baltic Sea and long-standing waves (seiches) develop. The seiche effect increases the sea-level along the southwestern coast and is amplified by the shallow bathymetry of the bays and basins within this part of the Baltic Sea and the prevalent exposure of the coastline to the east (Wolski and Wiśniewski, 2020). In the aforementioned weather setup along the southwestern coasts of the sea, the most extreme instrumentally measured MCF events occurred. The storm on November 11, 1872, associated with an easterly wind, caused a storm surge of up to ca. 3.3 m a.m.s.l. along the German coast. During the storm on October 20/21 2023, storm surge level rose up to 2.31 m above mean sea-level in narrow fjords opening to the east (Perlet-Markus, 2023).

The southern coasts of the Baltic Sea are most vulnerable to storms

associated with the third (iii) weather scenario (Rogers, 1997; Sztobryn et al., 2005; Sepp, 2009). When the storm lands, the prevailing north-westerly wind enhances wave set-up and runup on the north-facing shoreline of the southern Baltic. There, within the erodible, unconsolidated sedimentary coasts of retrogradational character and low-lying topography, the most extensive evidence for severe MCF events was documented such as within the i.e. Puck Bay, Mechelinki (Uściniowicz, Sz., et al., 2020; Leszczyńska et al., 2022) or Saaremaa Island, Estonia, in January 2005 (Suursaar et al., 2006; Tõnisson et al., 2008).

The Swedish coasts of the Baltic Sea as well as the shoreline of the Gulf of Bothnia are the least threatened by storm surges and MCF within the entire sea. The Swedish coast of the Baltic Sea is exposed in the direction opposite to the inflow of western air masses and opposite to the direction of low atmospheric pressure systems propagation (Wolski and Wiśniewski, 2020). Gulf of Bothnia is located away from the major mesoscale low-pressure centres tracks and is characterised by progradational, high topography resistant rock coast. The most severe MCF events described within this part of the Baltic Sea are associated with meteotsunamis (Pellikka et al., 2014, 2020).

2. Types of archives and study approaches

There are three major types of archives of storms and MCF events: sedimentary archives, historical archives and instrumental records. Sedimentary archives give insight into events most distant in time, up to 7000 cal. years BP within the Baltic Sea. In the case of the Baltic Sea historical archives start together with intense exploitation of the Baltic Sea by people, mainly after the 14th century. Instrumental records document phenomena within the recent ca. 200 years.

2.1. Sedimentary archives

2.1.1. Storms

Sedimentary archives of storms consist of geomorphological, sedimentological, and erosional features. They are found both onshore, where they primarily reflect wind activity and MCF (discussed separately), and offshore, where they are marked mainly by signatures of wind-generated waves and currents. In both environments, storm indicators have limited preservation potential, as they are prone to destruction and reworking due to subsequent waves, currents, wind and other postdepositional processes. Offshore archives of storm-induced erosion comprise scours within the nearshore bottom. The scours record events of rapid erosion of the bottom substrate due to highly energetic hydrodynamic conditions caused by waves associated with storms. Scours are formed by high near-bottom orbital wave activity and mark places from where the sediment was resuspended (Keen and Glenn, 2002). Offshore depositional archives of storms also encompass shore parallel bars (Van Rijn et al., 2018), tempestites and hummocky cross-stratification (HCS) (e.g. Milkert and Werner, 1996). The along-shore bars migrate onshore during storms, reflecting the near-bed orbital currents and wave asymmetry-related sand transport (van Rijn et al., 2018), while tempestites consist of sandy or silty beds in muddy sediment or, in shallower areas, of sandy HCS (Myrow, 2020). The storm related features of the sea-bottom are characterised based on bathymetric data and sediments are accessed by coring.

The most sound reconstructions of periods of more frequent storms, referred to as enhanced storminess periods, were produced from sedimentary archives of past aeolian activity, both, from coastal and inland areas, where more frequent storms cause intensification of aeolian processes. In the case of coastal areas with sufficient aeolian sand supply (Rotnicka and Dłużewski, 2019), when dunes are not stabilized by vegetation, storminess variation can be deciphered from repeated periods of enhanced dune formation, punctuated by periods of dune stabilization (Clemmensen et al., 2007, 2009, 2015). Sedimentary rhythms within coastal dunes record intra-annual changes in wind climate, including the intensity reflected in grain-size and direction through the

Fig. 4. Storminess regimes influencing low-lying topography sandy beaches and coastal wetlands (modified from Goslin and Clemmensen, 2017): A. swash regime, when only the beachface is reshaped by waves, berms are formed and sediments are transported offshore; B. collision regime, when the beach and beach barrier are impacted by waves, an erosional scarp is being created in the beach barrier or/and dunes, and intense offshore sediment transport occurs; C. Overwash regime, where the barrier system is broken and overwash features are being created; D. inundation regime, when the back-barrier area is flooded and sedimentary archives in the form of sandy or cryptic layers are being created.

internal stratification (Clemmensen et al., 2007). Coastal dunefield evolution is assessed from sedimentary structures within the dunes described from outcrops, trenches and geophysical surveys (ground penetrating radar) (Žuk et al., 2017; Clemmensen et al., 2009, 2015; Ludwig et al., 2017; Bierstedt et al., 2017). Clemmensen et al. (2016) proved that also barrier and backbarrier systems, including beach ridges, storm scarps and washover features can be used to reconstruct past storms and their frequency. Their research on Vesterlyng beach, at the Baltic Sea along the coast of Denmark allowed to relate height of these features to sea-level and wave setup during storms.

Multiple reconstructions of southern Scandinavian storminess spanning the last few hundred to a few thousand of years are based on presence of wind-transported particles deposited within inland, mostly organic, sedimentary successions (Björck and Clemmensen, 2004; de Jong et al., 2006; de Jong, 2007; Goslin et al., 2018, 2019; Sjöström, 2021; Sjöström et al., 2022; Kylander et al., 2013, 2016, 2018, 2023). The research on most recent changes of storminess based on aeolian,

mineral matter influx into bogs, peatbogs and mires (e.g. ASI – aeolian sand input, SMAR – sand mass accumulation rate or similar methods), correlated with instrumental records of the weather and sea-states from the eastern part of the Baltic Sea indicates that fluctuations in aeolian sand input represent well the variability in the frequency and intensity of storms, i.e. storminess and high influx in peat is associated with periods of frequent and intensive storm events (Vandel et al., 2019).

2.1.2. Marine coastal flooding (MCF)

The formation of sedimentary MCF archives is primarily influenced by depositional environment, available sediment sources, accommodation space, local morphology, MCF hydrodynamic conditions, inundation depth, and preservation potential (e.g., Bendixen et al., 2013; Goslin and Clemmensen, 2017; Engel et al., 2020; Szczuciński, 2008, 2020). In this review of sedimentary archives of MCF we focus on depositional evidence associated with different flooding regimes - swash, collision, overwash, and inundation (Fig. 4; Goslin and

Clemmensen, 2017) - with particular emphasis on the Baltic Sea coasts.

MCF sedimentary records linked to swash and collision regimes (Fig. 4A, B), typically driven by storm activity, primarily develop mainly along sandy and gravelly, low elevation, sediment-rich, progradational coasts. These environments often feature beach-ridge systems, whose evolution is largely controlled by sediment supply, sea level fluctuations, and wave action (Otvos, 2000; Scheffers et al., 2012). Composed of sand, gravel, pebble, and shell debris, these ridges form shore-parallel features extending tens to hundreds of meters and occasionally develop into extensive beach ridge plains. Such formations serve valuable archives of storm induced event frequency over the past few hundred to several thousand years (e.g., Bendixen et al., 2013; Clemmensen et al., 2014b; Lampe and Lampe, 2018; Suursaar et al., 2022).

Overwash deposits (washovers) are typically associated with severe storms, hurricanes and associated MCF events (e.g., Leatherman et al., 1977; Donnelly et al., 2004; Wang and Horwitz, 2007) or even minor tsunamis (e.g., Ishimura et al., 2022). They form in the overwash flooding regime (Fig. 4C), as a result of overtopping and breaching of sandy barriers, beach ridges, and dune systems. Washover features typically consist of well-sorted sandy bodies within barrier, lagoonal, or back-barrier deposits and usually exhibiting a fan-like geometry (Morton and Sallenger, 2003) with varied sedimentary structures, e.g., planar bedding, low-angle cross-bedding, graded bedding, or foreset lamination dipping in a landward direction (e.g., Leatherman et al., 1977; Schwartz, 1982; Phantuwongraj et al., 2013; Moskalewicz et al., 2020). Their formation is driven by storm surge and wave run-up exceeding the height of the coastal barrier, leading to erosion that creates overwash channels or results in barrier breaching. Additional controlling factors include sediment availability, accommodation space in the back-barrier environment, post-depositional processes (e.g., wind-driven redeposition and dune formation), and human interventions (Morton and Sallenger, 2003; Lazarus et al., 2020; Moskalewicz et al., 2024). It is not always clear if particular washovers originate from a single extreme event or represent the cumulative effect of multiple storm events. Some washovers show evidence of event stratigraphy, while others appear homogenized due to post-depositional reworking. Switzer and Jones (2008) suggested that multiphase structures recording successive overwash events are rare (Switzer and Jones, 2008). Other studies have expanded on this issue, demonstrating that some of such landforms may form for decades, evolving in size and morphology over time (Lazarus et al., 2020; Rodriguez et al., 2020).

The most variable and complex sedimentary archives of MCF events of various origins (extreme storms, tsunami, infragravity waves etc.) form under inundation regime when water overtops coastal dunes or barriers (Fig. 4D). The flooding water erodes and transport sediments ranging from mud to boulders, depositing them across the inundated area, primarily in low energy, backbarrier environments such as lakes, lagoons, and wetlands (e.g., Liu and Fearn, 1993; Fan and Liu, 2008; Switzer and Jones, 2008; Costa and Andrade, 2020; Engel et al., 2020). These deposits manifest as chaotic boulder accumulations (e.g., Goto et al., 2010; Costa et al., 2011; Cox et al., 2018), discrete, often stratified, layers (e.g., Donnelly et al., 2004; Kortekaas and Dawson, 2007; Jan-kaew et al., 2008; Lambert et al., 2008; Morton et al., 2007; Williams et al., 2016; Piotrowski et al., 2017; Suursaar and Tönisson, 2017; Swindles et al., 2018; Spiske, 2020) or cryptic event layers indistinguishable to unaided eye (Hess et al., 2024; Nakanishi et al., 2023; Pleskot et al., 2023; Leszczyńska et al., 2024). MCF deposits typically contain a mix of offshore, beach, dune and back-barrier sediments (e.g. soil) and range from a few to several tens of centimeters of thickness, generally thinning and fining landward. Their basal contact is often abrupt and undulating due to irregular antecedent topography (Morton et al., 2007).

Identifying MCF deposits requires analyzing multiple characteristics, including spatial geometry, sedimentary structures, grain size, micro-morphology, stratigraphic relationships, erosional features, sediment provenance, and geochemical, mineralogical, and micropaleontological

proxies. Additional evidence includes saltwater indicators, archaeological records, and geomorphological markers (e.g., Morton et al., 2007; Goff et al., 2012; Chagué-Goff et al., 2017; Costa and Andrade, 2020; Engel et al., 2020). Despite this broad analytical approach, distinguishing between different MCF types remains challenging without precise dating or historical records. In particular, distinguishing storm surge from tsunami deposits remains debated, with no universal indicator - local geological and environmental context must always be considered (e.g., Morton et al., 2007; Kortekaas and Dawson, 2007; Vött et al., 2019; Costa and Andrade, 2020; Yap et al., 2021). Moreover, post-depositional modifications further complicate MCF identification (Spiske et al., 2020; Szczuciński, 2020). Some changes occur soon after deposition, while others continue for decades. For example, wind-driven reworking of MCF deposits associated with both tsunami (Richmond et al., 2012) and hurricane (Williams, 2015) can rapidly alter their thickness and extent. While long-term processes such as soil formation may cause sediment mixing, microfossil dissolution, and chemical alterations, potentially obscuring or erasing the MCF record (Szczuciński, 2020).

The variability of MCF event deposits, regardless of their formation regime, necessitates a wide range of methods applied across various spatial scales (see for instance Engel et al., 2020 for more details). The initial investigation of all types of sedimentary archives of MCF includes field techniques, morphological analysis (e.g., beach ridges) and understanding of local context to characterize depositional environments. At sites where MCF event deposits are identified, describing their architecture - particularly inland extent and alongshore continuity - is essential for further analysis. This is typically achieved through geophysical surveys (e.g., ground penetrating radar), trenching, soil sampling and borehole investigations. Once potential MCF deposits or cryptic records are identified, a comprehensive suite of laboratory analyses is conducted. These include sedimentary structure assessments (at macro- and microscale) to determine emplacement processes, compositional analyses (e.g., grain size, microfossils, mineralogy, and geochemistry) to confirm marine provenance, and dating techniques to estimate event chronology. Below are briefly summarized some of the commonly used techniques.

Macroscopic analysis of sedimentary structures - such as lamination, cross-lamination, intercalated mud layers, and flame structures - provides insights into formation mechanisms and the number of inundations (Morton et al., 2007; Spiske, 2020). Features like burrows and other deformations can further inform the post-depositional history of sediments (Szczuciński, 2020). Recent advancements, including micro-morphology and micro-CT scanning (Brandon et al., 2014), enable the identification of fine-scale internal structures. For example, Falvard and Paris (2017) and Leszczyńska et al. (2022) documented rip-up clasts of the underlying substratum within event deposit layers - key diagnostic features indicative of rapid flow and soil erosion in tsunami and storm deposits, respectively.

Granulometry of the MCF event deposits is a useful criterion in differentiating marine inundation deposits from background sedimentation (e.g. Leszczyńska et al., 2024; Moskalewicz et al., 2024) and provides insight into flow velocity (e.g., Jaffe et al., 2012). Poor sorting indicates multiple sources of sediments, relatively short transport path, and a shallow flow depth (Boldt et al., 2010; Piotrowski et al., 2017). Alternating laminae of coarse and fine particles indicate multiple high-frequency waves. The robustness of grain-size data as a proxy for the identification of MCF deposits can be enhanced through statistical analysis (Hess et al., 2024; Goslin and Clemmensen, 2017). Statistical methods such as principal component analysis, cluster analysis, end-member analysis or linear discriminant analyses allow for the identification of event deposits based on grain-size data, even in sedimentary successions, where visible sand layers are absent (Leszczyńska et al., 2024).

The presence of shells, shell debris, and marine microfossils is commonly used as an indicator of the offshore origin of the deposits left

by MCF events. The occurrence, abundance, and types of diatoms, dinoflagellates and foraminifera serve as valuable proxies for identifying marine influence (Morton et al., 2007; Fan and Liu, 2008; Kortekaas and Dawson, 2007; Pilarczyk et al., 2016).

Recently, a novel approach using sedimentary ancient DNA (sedaDNA) has been tested for MCF deposits, yielding promising results. Studies suggest that the DNA of marine organisms can be preserved in MCF event deposits, even in the absence of a microfossil record - an issue commonly encountered with carbonate-based foraminiferal tests in the typically low-pH environments of coastal wetlands (Szczuciński et al., 2016). Furthermore, environmental sedaDNA analysis may offer a valuable tool for distinguishing between tsunami and storm deposits (Yap et al., 2021).

The mineral composition of MCF deposits can also aid in identifying offshore sediment provenance, as demonstrated through heavy mineral analysis by Costa et al. (2018) and Moskalewicz et al. (2022). However, variations in mineral density and their segregation within event deposits may also reflect the hydrodynamic conditions of MCF. This effect is particularly evident among heavy minerals, which, as shown by Jagodziński et al. (2009), aid to differentiation between MCF types, such as storm and tsunami deposits.

Organic and inorganic geochemistry is useful not only for tracing the origin of event sediments but also for providing evidence of seawater inundation (e.g., Sabatier et al., 2010, 2012; Degeai et al., 2015; Das et al., 2013; Chagué-Goff et al., 2017). The method is particularly valuable in cases, where visible sedimentary layers are absent (e.g., Chagué-Goff et al., 2012). In sediment-starved coastal systems, MCF events may transport minute amounts of sediment, leaving salinity-related elements in the topsoil as the only evidence of marine inundation. Although this approach has limitations in the Baltic Sea due to its low salinity, several successful studies have applied geochemical analyses to storm deposits along its southern coast (Piotrowski et al., 2017; Leszczyńska et al., 2022). The elements most commonly used as marine indicators include sodium, sulphur and chlorine; however, because they are highly soluble and prone to migration (e.g., Chagué-Goff et al., 2017; Szczuciński, 2020), more conservative indicators of seawater influence, such as calcium, strontium or magnesium are often preferred. These elements can also serve as proxies for carbonate materials, including shell fragments (e.g., Fan and Liu, 2008; Das et al., 2013; Xiong et al., 2018). However, in order to answer the question on marine versus other origin of the deposits, geochemical parameters have to be used in combination, using any single element will not present with unequivocal evidence for the origin of the sediments.

In the case of organic matter indicators such as TOC/TN ratio, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ provide with evidence of marine, terrestrial and freshwater origin of sediments (Lamb et al., 2007; Das et al., 2013). The differentiation of MCF versus other origin deposits has been tested and described in detail based on the examples of sediments from sheltered lakes occasionally flooded by storms (Lambert et al., 2008; Das et al., 2013). Organic matter of marine origin have lower TOC/TN ratio and heavier $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ than terrestrial one (Lambert et al., 2008; Goff et al., 2012) and the sediments from the coastal lakes represent two different geochemical states: one representing lake isolated from the influence of the seawater, characterised by low $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and the other, representing the lake after flooding by the marine water, characterised by higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}$.

Establishing the age of storm events from sediments either relies on the direct dating of storm deposits and morphological features or indirect dating by establishing the maximum and minimum age of the event from over- and underlying sediments. In the case of direct age estimation these are deposits of sand, gravel and pebble layers and/or beach ridges or overwash features which are being dated. The most suitable method of direct dating in the case of these is optically stimulated luminescence (OSL), where time spans of decades to millennia can be covered (Brill et al., 2012; Cunha et al., 2010). The advantages of this method are that it is performed on quartz and feldspar mineral particles, which abundantly occur within the coastal zone. The limitation of this technique is

Table 2

Baltic storms documented in chronicles and annals from the beginning of the 14th to the end of the 18th century. Information on storms marked with * comes from handwritten notes on the margins of chronicles, which postdate the date of publication of the source.

No.	Date	Location	Source
1	1304 or 1307, 1 November	Mecklenburg	Baier, R. (ed.) 1893, p. 3, 17
	1320, 30 November	Lübeck	Grauthoff, F. H. (ed.), 1829, p. 439
2	1357	Denmark	Langebek, J. (ed.), 1786, pp. 530–531; compare. HUB, 3, Nr 419
3	1361, 14 September	Gdańsk	Curicke, R., 1687, p. 278 Grunau S., 1876, Tract. 13, cap. 2 Henneberger C., 1595, p. 67
4	1370, 3 December	Mecklenburg	Crull, F. (ed.), 1878, p. 184
5	1374, 4 December	Lübeck	Koppmann K. (ed.), 1899a, p. 251
6	1398, 5–6 July	Lübeck	Koppmann K. (ed.), 1899b, p. 102
7	1403	Dithmarchen Land	Dahlmann, F.C. (ed.) 1827, pp. 377–378
8	1412, 21 November		Koppmann, K., (ed.) 1899, p. 162
9	1436, 4 October	Kalmar, Gotland	Schwalm, J. (ed.), 1895, p. 564.
10	1436, before 1 November	Lübeck	Schwalm, J. (ed.), 1895, p. 564
11	1449, 14–16 October	Mecklenburg	Mohnicke, G.C.E., Zober, E. H. (eds.), 1933, pp. 192–193
12	1455, after 12 June	Mecklenburg	
13	1465, 16 November	Gdańsk Bay	Hirsch Th. (ed.), 1870a, pp. 626–627
14	1467, 28–29 January	Mecklenburg	Baier, R. (ed.) 1893, pp. 39–40
15	1468, 21 October	Gdańsk Bay	Hirsch Th. (ed.), 1870b, p. 731
16	1473, 16 April	Mecklenburg	Mohnicke, G.C.E., Zober, E. H. (eds.), 1933, p. 13
17	1476, 15/16 October	Schleswig-Holstein	Baier, R. (ed.) 1893, p. 45
18	1477, 29 September	Gdańsk Bay	Hirsch Th. (ed.), 1870b, p. 740
19	1479, 29 September	Gdańsk Bay	Hirsch Th. (ed.), 1870b, p. 743
20	1482, 8 July	Gdańsk Bay	Hirsch Th. (ed.), 1870c, p. 719; Henneberger C., 1595, p. 79; Curicke, R., 1687, p. 278
21	1482, 8 September	Gdańsk Bay	Hirsch, Th. (ed.), 1874a, p. 497
22	1484 (between March and December)	Meklemburgia	Krabit 1619, lib. XIII, cap. XL and lib. XIV, cap. I, p. 479–482; comp. Hanseresse, I, 1, nr 582; Henneberger C., 1595, p. 80
23	1486, 2 July	Gdańsk	Grunau S., 1876, Tract. 18, cap. 10; Curicke, R., 1687, p. 278
24	1488, 10 April	Gdańsk, Leba	Hirsch Th. (ed.), 1870b, p. 768
25	1488, 6 October–25 November	Schonen - Gdańsk	Hirsch Th. (ed.), 1870b, p. 771
26	1490, 1 November	Spit, Samland	Hirsch Th. (ed.), 1870b, p. 781
27	1491, 14 September	Holstein	Lappenberg, J.M. (ed.), 1861, p. 262
28	1492, 5 May	Gdańsk Bay	Hirsch Th. (ed.), 1870b, p. 793
29	1495, 28 October	Stockholm	

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

No.	Date	Location	Source
30	1497, 15–17 September	southern Baltic coast	Hirsch, Th. (ed.), 1874b, pp. 447–448; HUB, Bd. 11, Nr 1034, 1035, 1036, 1037, 1038, 1042, 1045, 1050, 1057, 1058, 1059, 1060, 1061, 1062, 1070
31	1499, 18–19 January	southern Baltic coast	Mohnicke, G.C.E., Zober, E. H. (eds.), 1933, p. 215
32	1509, 5–8 November	Gdańsk Bay	Strehlke F., Strehlke, E., 1873, p. 658–659
33	1515, 2 February	Gdańsk Bay	Archiwum Państwowe Gdańsk, 300, R/L.I., no. 9, p. 533
34	1515, 8–14 March	southern Baltic coast	Gaebel, G. (ed.), 1908, p. 103
35	1516, 20 May	Gdańsk Bay	Strehlke F., Strehlke, E., 1873, p. 659
36	1521, November	Lübeck area	Dahlmann, F.C. (ed.) 1827, p. 548
37	1531, 29 September	Samland	Arnold U. (ed.), 1986, p. 223–224
38	1542, 27 July	Pomerania	Girguš R. et al. (ed.), 1965, p. 137
39	1558, 11–13 January, 8 February	Darłowo	Girguš R. et al. (ed.), 1965, p. 147–148
40	1616, 25 May	Gdańsk	Curicke, R., 1687, p. 279
41	1619, 30 July	Pomerania	Weikinn C. (ed.), 1961, p. 109
42	1624, 20 February	Greifswald	Weikinn C. (ed.), 1961, p. 132
43	1625	Lübeck	Weikinn C. (ed.), 1961, p. 498
44	1634, 21 October	Schleswig	Weikinn C. (ed.), 1961, p. 171
45	1637, 3 March	Gdańsk	Biblioteka PAN, MS 915, Hancke Michał
46	1637, 20 August	Gdańsk	Biblioteka PAN, MS 915, Hancke Michał
47	1642, 15 February	Hamburg	Weikinn C. (ed.), 1961, p. 200; Girguš R. 2022, p. 32
No.	Date	Location	Source
48	1648, 25 February	Northern Germany	Weikinn C. (ed.), 1961, p. 221; Girguš 2022, p. 35
49	1649, 13–15, 23 October	Barth, Mecklenburg	Weikinn C. (ed.), 1961, p. 228; Girguš 2022, p. 35–36
50	1663, 17 September	Pomerania	Weikinn C. (ed.), 1961, p. 352; Girguš 2022, p. 54
51	1675, 17–18 November	Gdańsk, Königsberg	Curicke, p. 428; Namaczyńska 1937, pp. 82–83
52	1693, 10, 20 January	Barth, Mecklenburg	Weikinn C. (ed.), 1961, p. 491; Girguš 2022, p. 84
53	1693, 25 October	Kamień Pomorski	Weikinn C. (ed.), 1961, p. 495; Girguš R., 2022, p. 85
54	1693, 17 December	Gdańsk	Strehlke F., Strehlke, E., 1873, p. 660; Weikinn, p. 495; Girguš R., 2022, p. 85
55	1694, 10–11 February	Lübeck, Kiel, Warnemünde, Kopenhagen, Wismar	Weikinn C. (ed.), 1961, p. 498; Girguš 2022, p. 86
56	1694, 20 February	The Baltic	Weikinn C. (ed.), 1961, p. 497; Girguš 2022, p. 86
57	1718, 16–18 March	Pregola, Königsberg	Weikinn C. (ed.), 1963, p. 131; Girguš 2022, p. 112
58	1730, 17 December, 23 December	Kamień Pomorski, Wolin, Kołobrzeg, Gdańsk	Weikinn, 1963, pp. 180, 229; Kuryer Polski 1730 (53); Girguš R., 2022 pp. 120–121
59	1736, 15 November	Gdańsk Bay	Pamiętniki Dawida Brauera, APToruń, Kat. II, XIII-54.
60	1737, 31 January *	Gdańsk	Curicke, R., 1687, p. 322
61	1747, (day unknown) *	Gdańsk	Curicke, R., 1687, p. 331

Table 2 (continued)

No.	Date	Location	Source
62	1771, 20 November	Sund, Göthenburg, Rewel, Ryfa, Gdańsk, Kronstadt, Saint Petersburg	Wiadomości Warszawskie 1772/2, pp. 6–7; Girguš 2022, p. 121

uncertainty of the age of the event, reaching up to 300 to 600 years in a range of 6000 years, which may further reinforced by incomplete bleaching of the mineral grains, another constraint is the accuracy of background dose rate determination, which in complex coastal stratigraphies poses a problem (Brill and Tamura, 2020).

The maximum or minimum age of the MCF event can be indirectly established by means of radiocarbon dating. In order to accurately interpret the dates and delimit the age of the event the context of a sample taken for dating with respect to the MCF layer must be recognized and documented (Piotrowski et al., 2017; Kelsey and Witter, 2020). Further, obtained calibrated dates should be framed within a Bayesian model to provide accurate event age (Kelsey and Witter, 2020). The limitation of the method is the fact that it does not date the exact timing of the event, but establishes its maximum and minimum age. Maximum age may altered by significant erosion of underlying deposits, pushing the age obtained up to few tens to even few thousands of years back in time. The minimum age on the contrary, may be artificially young due to the time-laps between the event and the restitution of ecological conditions in the flooded are (Ishizawa et al., 2017). Moreover, for very recent deposits within the timespan of few tens to about one hundred years the direct age of MCF deposits may be established based on the ^{210}Pb or ^{37}Cs radionuclides (e.g., Arnaud et al., 2002; Sanchez-Cabeza and Ruiz-Fernández, 2012; Arias-Ortiz et al., 2018; Moskalewicz et al., 2020).

2.2. Historical archives

Exploration of storms within the Baltic Sea is not a common focus in historical research and the first studies – published catalogues and research works related to meteorological events – date from the late 19th and the beginning of the 20th century CE (i.e. Toeppen, 1894; Henning, 1904). An early work by Matysik (1950), who explored ancient maritime law (“*ius naufragii*”), reveals that storms were mainly reported and described in documents as a background for legal disputes on merchants’ losses of goods at sea and claims for compensation. Mozdzeń (2016) studied historical sources in search for cultural aspects of storms. He reported storms as rare, unusual, and culturally significant occurrences that evoke strong social emotions (e.g., Mozdzeń, 2016). Other examples of review of historical sources describing storms and their influence on urbanized stretches of the coast, most importantly ports and settlements (cf. Tables 2 and 3), encompass works by Długocki (1996) and Toeppen (1894), who explored accounts reporting changes of the Vistula Spit during the Middle Ages to the second half of the 15th and the beginning of the 16th century. In all cited accounts the main reported topic was the formation of new inlets and the filling of old ones. Similarly, a review of historical sources targeting the influence of storms on the deepening or shallowing of certain coastal areas of the Baltic, such as the ‘Nye Deep’ near Rügen and Stralsund, has been explored.

In reviewed historical accounts, the term “storm” appears as subjective and most often considered as stormy weather with wind and rainfall and significant wave height, often with some coastal flooding. The vast majority of sources mentioning storms were written in Latin or old German languages and originated from territories mainly along the southern and western Baltic Sea coast. References to storms within the Baltic Sea region are documented in two main types of written historical sources: i) administrative sources, such as public documents, reports, accounts books (Table 3), and ii) narrative sources, such as chronicles,

Table 3

Baltic storms documented in the ‘Hanserecesse’ (HR) and in the ‘Hanseatisches Urkundenbuch’ (HUB) from the beginning of the 14th to the end of the 15th century.

No.	Date	Location	Source
1	1342, before 3 December	Gedser, Denmark	HUB, Bd. 2, nr 725
2	before 23 October [1369]	Sund	HR, Bd. 3, Abt. 1, Nr 32
3	1373 (or before)	Oeresund, Gronesund	HUB, 4, 442; HR 1, Abt. II, Nr 56
4	1387	Pomerania	HUB, 4, Nr 885
5	1388 (or before)	ca. Danemark	HR, Bd. 1, Abt. III, Nr 383, 384, 396
6	1389 (or before)	Bornholm	HUB 4, Nr 957
7	1391, after 16 September	North Sea, Baltic Sea?	HUB, Bd. 4, Nr 1065
8	1393, June	ca. Copenhagen	HUB, Bd. 5, nr 105, footnote 1
9	1393, before 3 July	Zealand	HUB, Bd. 5, Nr 105
10	1393, before 27 November	Wismar	HR, Bd. 4, I, Nr 169
11	1394, before 2 July	Trave	HUB, Bd. 5, Nr 168
12	1396	Danemark	HR Bd. 1, Abt. IV, Nr 154, par. 3; Nr 350, par. 9; Nr 445, 469, par. 3; nr 477, par. 4 and 5; nr 618, par. 8.
13	1401, before 30 April	between Hamburg and Frisia	HR, Bd. 5, Abt. I, Nr 19
14	1404, 28 September	On the road to Flanders	HR, Bd. 8, Abt. I, Nr 1032
15	1407, before 10 Mai 1407 (9–10?)	ca. Lübeck	HR, Bd. 5, I, Nr 401
16	1416, 16/17/18 July	ca. Flensburg, Kiel Bay	HR, Bd. 6, Abt. I, Nr 262
17	1419, before 21 March	ca. Hamburg	HR, Bd. 7, Abt. I, Nr 19
18	1423, autumn	ca. Wiborg	HR, Bd. 7, Abt. I, Nr 639
19	1423, before 20 December	Trave, Großenbrode	HUB, Bd. 6, Nr 531
20	1428, before 20 June	Reveshol, ca. Copenhagen	HR, Bd. 8, Abt. I, Nr 447
21	1428, before 25 July	between Lübeck, Wismarem and Rostock	HR, Bd. 8, Abt. 1, nr 470
22	1428, before 19 October	south Baltic coast	HUB, Bd. 6, Nr 764
23	1430, before 23 March	Sund	HUB, Bd. 6, nr 851
24	1430, before 28 December	Schleswig, Rostock, Wismar	HR, Bd. 8, Abt. I, nr 845
25	1434, before 11 March	ca. Gdańsk	HUB, Bd. 7, Nr 13
26	1435, before 15 August	by Falster	HR, Bd. 1, Abt. II, Nr 456
27	1435, before 12 October	The mouth of the Vistula river	HUB, Bd. 7, nr 135
28	1436, ca. 10 October	Hamburg	HR, Bd. 2, Abt. II, Nr 54
29	1439, 21 February	Baltic Sea	HUB, Bd. 7, nr 767
30	1440, before 12 April	ca. Gdańsk	HUB, Bd. 7, nr 555
31	1441, before 14 April	Belt	HR, Bd. 2, Abt. II, Nr 457
32	1443, before 7 August	Wisby	HR, Bd. 3, II, Nr 24
33	1444, before 10 June	Kołobrzeg	HR, Bd. 3, Abt. II, Nr 154
34	1447, before 11 July	Sund	HR, Bd. 3, Abt. II, Nr 317
35	1447, 1. half of year	–	HR, Bd. 3, II, footnote 1
36	1455, autumn	Gotland	HUB, Bd. 8, Nr 456
37	1456, before 24 December	Lipau	HUB, Bd. 8, Nr 518
38	1457, autumn	ca. Gdańsk	HUB, Bd. 8, Nr 663, footnote 4
39	1457	ca. Gdańsk	HUB, Bd. 8, Nr 738
40	1459, before 20 Mai	Wolin	HUB, Bd. 8, Nr 800
41	1459, before 18 November	ca. Hamburg	HUB, Bd. 8, Nr 856
42	1461, before 25 April	Greifswald	HR, Bd. 5, Abt. 2, Nr 79
43	1461, before 8 September	Gotland	HUB, Bd. 8, Nr 1072
44	1466, 1 October	Riga Bay	HR, Bd. 5, Abt. 2, Nr 833
45	1464, before 8 August	between Lübeck and Stralsund	HUB, Bd. 9, Nr 121
46	1472, before 6 January	Flanders coast	HR, Bd. 6, Abt. 2, Nr 509
47	1472	ca. Lübeck	HR, Bd. 6, Abt. 2, Nr 572

Table 3 (continued)

No.	Date	Location	Source
48	1472, before 13 July	Livland, ca. Kaunas	HUB, Bd. 10, Nr 128
49	1472, before 22 July (presumably before 13 July)	Courland	HUB, Bd. 10, Nr 131; por. nr 188
50	1473, between 22 September - 3 October	between Amsterdam aand Lübeck	HR, Bd. 7, Abt. 2, Nr 51
51	1477, before 26 October	Pomeranian coast	HUB, Bd. 10, Nr 595
52	1477, autumn	ca. Copenhagen	HUB, Bd. 10, Nr 618
53	1482, before 6 Mai	ca. Gdańsk	HUB, Bd. 10, Nr 966
54	1482, before 25 October	Baltic Sea	HUB, Bd. 10, Nr 1014
55	1483, before 1 February	The mouth of Elbe	HUB, Bd. 10, Nr 1032
56	1483, before 23 April	ca. Lübeck	HR, Bd. 1., Abt. 3, Nr 330
57	1484, 15 July	ca. Copenhagen	HR, Bd. 1, Abt. 3, Nr 547
58	1484, ca. 29 June – 16 August	ca. Gdańsk	HR, Bd. 1, Abt. 3, Nr 547
59	1484, before 5 August	ca. Gdańsk	HR, Bd. 1, Abt. 3, Nr 547
60	1484, ca. 29 June – 16 August	between Sund and Gdańsk	HR, Bd. 1, Abt. 3, Nr 547
61	1484, 13 July	ca. Copenhagen	HR, Bd. 1, Abt. 3, Nr 547
62	1487, before 23 Mai	ca. Lübeck	HUB, Bd. 11, Nr 133
63	1487, late autumn	ca. Stokholm	HUB, Bd. 11, Nr 170
64	1488, before 13 January	Sandön	HUB, Bd. 11, Nr 197
65	1488, November–December	Coast of Samogitia	HUB, Bd. 11, nr 261
66	1489, autumn	On the road from Bremem to Riga	HUB, Bd. 11, Nr 328
67	1490, autumn	between Rewel and Lübeck	HUB, Bd. 11, Nr 461
68	1490, before 1 December	ca. Gdańsk	HUB, Bd. 11, Nr 404
69	1491, winter 1490/91	between Eastern Baltic Sea and Kampen	HUB, Bd. 11, Nr 429
70	1491, ca. 25 November	Danemark	HUB, Bd. 11, Nr 540
71	1492	between Gdańsk and West	HUB, Bd. 11, Nr 755
72	1492, winter	between Lund and Gdańsk	HUB, Bd. 11, Nr 605
73	1492, before 7 February	the mouth of Elbe	HUB, Bd. 11, Nr 546
74	1492, before 6 March (before 7 February?)	the mouth of Elbe	HUB, Nr 552
75	1492, after 30 October	Zealand	HUB, Bd. 11, nr 710
76	1493, before 26 January	Perdelsalin, Finland	HUB, Bd. 11, nr 643
77	1493, before 14 June	the mouth of Elbe	HUB, Bd. 11, nr 677
78	1493, before 12 November	Seeland	HR, Bd. 3, Abt. 3, Nr 289
79	1497, September	–	HUB, Bd. Nr 1034, 1035, 1036, 1037, 1038, 1042, 1045, 1049
80	1499, after 29 April	Windau	HUB, Bd. 11, nr 1134

annals, diaries, private correspondence (Table 2). Notices in chronicles, annals, and official correspondance between Hanseatic towns and tradesman are the main source of knowledge on storms from the 13th to the end of 15th century (Medieval period). These descriptions are often of concise format, indicating the occurrence of the storm with comments on challenges in shipping, often attributed to adverse *windes und stormes halven* (wind and storm). The resultant damage is described. Chronicles and annals of that time give particularly detailed accounts of the most severe events, such as for example storms in 1398 and 1412 described in numerous narrative sources, among others in continuation of Lübeck Detmar-Chronik von 1395–1399 (Detmar-Chronik, in: Die Chroniken der Deutschen Städte vom 14. bis ins 16. Jahrhundert, Bd. 26) or a storm in 1497 described in many narrative sources, especially thoroughly in Kolberg (Kołobrzeg) city chronicles (Riemann, 1873). A unique example of historical sources containing storm-related information are chronicles with annotations in the margins made by their owners or readers. For instance, Reinhold Curicke (1610–1667), a 17th-century historian from Gdańsk, documented the significant storms in Gdańsk’s history in his work “Der Stadt Dantzick historische Beschreibung”, published in

Amsterdam in 1687, using an array of older chronicles.

The dates of discrete storms described in historical sources of both kinds, differ by several days, up to two weeks. By attempts of exact dating of storms in numerous cases, only the ‘terminus ante quem’ (date before) and ‘post quem’ (after) of such an event can be identified, allowing for the possibility that it might be a storm referenced in one of the chronicles.

While numerous references to storms exist in the historical sources it is challenging to accurately define the scale of described events. The documentation of storms in the past centuries was predominantly based on subjective perception. In chronicles and annals only the most severe storms were mentioned. However, in the documents and correspondence describing maritime activities during stormy conditions and losses caused by these events, also medium scale storms were described. The vessels used in the 13th to 15th century on the Baltic, such as liburnas, cogs (with a displacement of up to about 200–300 tons), or hulks, were not resistant to stormy conditions and even 60 km/h wind speeds could pose a significant threat to these vessels (Schnall, 1998; Hirte and Wolf, 1998). Moreover, some of the ships, such as caravels, might have been at risk even from weaker winds that are not currently classified as storms.

Only a portion of documents from administrative and narrative sources has been published within various publishing series, typically up to around 1500 CE (e.g., Hanserecesse, Hansisches Urkundenbuch) (Table 3). From the beginning of the 16th century there is a notable increase in the number of available sources. While chronicles, annals, documents, and correspondence remained pivotal, new sources emerged, including handwritten newspapers or written forecasts, which sometimes comprised insights to atmospheric conditions. As an example may serve the vast documentation on the extreme storm event from 1872 described *inter alia* in Baensch (1875), Colding (1881) and Clemmensen et al. (2014a). Over time, the private correspondence gained in significance, and from the 18th century onward, the printed press played a crucial role in documenting and disseminating information about storms and related phenomena including storm surges and MCF. Despite the wealth of information, many of these sources remain unpublished in print. In the most recent history, up to few decades, documentary sources, including news reports and insurance or government compensation records, are relevant also in the instrumental era, as they provide information on the socioeconomic impacts of coastal floods. Knowledge of storms, including their frequency and intensity, can also be supplemented by various documents such as flood hazard assessments and administrative reports. Additionally, extensive information on past events from the recent history can be found in national preliminary flood hazard assessments mandated by the European Union, which are collectively available via the European Environment Agency (2024).

2.3. Instrumental record

2.3.1. Storms

One of the major effects of consecutive storms and associated wind, rainfall and wave action onshore is beach and cliff retreat (Terefenko et al., 2018). However, this geomorphological evidence of storm activity, is discussed in the instrumental record section as once not measured instrumentally just after the storm event, reshaped by following coastal processes they may not be unequivocally ascribed to erosional effect of storm. Geomorphological archives of storm activity most often are surveyed by means of remote sensing – satellite images, maps and LIDAR data analysis (Uściłowicz, G., et al., 2014; Terefenko et al., 2018, 2020; Tysiąc et al., 2025).

Instrumental records of hydrological and meteorological parameters associated with storms and storm surges include long-term low-frequency sea-level observations, tide-gauge measurements, and satellite altimetry data, as well as air pressure and wind speed records, dating back to the late 18th century CE. The Baltic Sea currently has one of the most comprehensive high-resolution tide-gauge networks in the world.

A total of 85 tide-gauge stations in the Baltic Sea are documented in the Permanent Service for Mean Sea-Level (PSMSL) data base, where monthly data are compiled (PSMSL Data Explorer, 2024; Weisse et al., 2021). Notably, 27 stations around the Baltic Sea have recorded over 100 years of monthly data. One of the longest continuous sea-level observation series is available for Stockholm (Ekman, 2003) with mareograph data extending back to 1889, and weekly or daily observational data dating as far as back 1774. Other significant long-term records include tide-gauge data in Świnoujście, Poland (starting in 1811), Travemünde, Germany (1829), Öland Island, Sweden (1851), and Liepāja, Lithuania (1865) (Bogdanov et al., 2000; Wiśniewski and Wolski, 2009; Wiśniewski et al., 2009; Männikus et al., 2020; Kelln et al., 2022).

Collected by national meteorological and hydrological institutes, the tide-gauge data are mostly public and available through international databases. Other collective providers of up-to-date sea-level data include the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS), the University of Hawaii Sea Level Center (UHSLC) and the Global Extreme Sea Level Analysis (GESLA) v3 dataset (Haigh et al., 2022). The latter one contains hourly data for 160 gauges in the Baltic Sea and Danish Straits (without Skagerrak), with an average data coverage of 28 years per gauge station, constituting some one-fourth of tide-gauge data available for Europe as a whole.

Supplementary to tide-gauge records is satellite altimetry data, which provide comprehensive coverage of the whole Baltic Sea area (Legeais et al., 2018). Daily data at 0.125° resolution starting at 1 January 1993 is available from CMEMS. The long-term sea-level trends provide the mandatory framework for the recognition of storms as short-term extreme sea-level events.

In analyses of storm weather setup surface air pressure is also relevant factor. However, one of the first instrumental air pressure measurements were conducted in southern Sweden since 1787 (Barring and Fortuniak, 2009), and in northernmost Denmark (Skagen) since 1860 (Clemmensen et al., 2014a), barometers only became widely used in the region from the 1920s onward. As with other types of such data, also meteorological observations are mostly accessible through international consortia. Daily wind speed and air pressure are available for individual stations around the Baltic Sea at high density via the European Climate Assessment and Dataset (part of a broader international effort, Van den Besselaar et al., 2015), as well as in gridded, interpolated format (E-OBS, Cornes et al., 2018).

Both, hydrological and meteorological observations suffer from low frequency of measurements, and/or short data series (Rutgersson et al., 2015). Therefore, to achieve more comprehensive and homogenous coverage of the Baltic Sea area climate and ocean reanalysis is used (Rutgersson et al., 2015). In the reanalysis, a numerical 3D-model simulation is run where available observations are assimilated at every time step in order to achieve the best approximation of the state of the atmosphere and ocean. For meteorological variables, the latest global climate reanalysis ERA5 (Hersbach et al., 2020, 2023) is the primary source. It provides hourly data since 1940 up to just a few days behind real time, including detailed wind speed, gust and directional data, air pressure and large variety of wave parameters (Hersbach et al., 2020). The resolution for meteorological variables is 0.25° and for hydrological ones it is 0.5°. Longer reanalysis is available, with 20CR (20th Century Reanalysis) going back to 1836, though at the cost of much lower resolution (Slivinski et al., 2019). Sea-level data is available from models that use wind and air pressure from ERA5 reanalysis, such as the Deltares Global Tide and Surge Model, which covers period 1979–2018 in 0.1° resolution at 10-min timesteps (Muis et al., 2020). For the period of 20 years, between 1992 and 2012, sea-level is available from a dedicated Baltic Sea reanalysis (Fu et al., 2012). CMEMS makes available data at very high, 1 nautical mile spatial resolution, but only at daily time steps for the period 1993–2022. There are also examples of research in which machine-learning methods are applied to extend the existing data based on nearby stations and complementary data (Hieronymous and Kalén, 2020; Dubois et al., 2024a, 2024b).

Table 4

Number of publications on the MCF/storms/storminess events between 7000 BP and 14th century within the Baltic Sea grouped based the: A. country in which the research was undertaken (PL = Poland, GER = Germany, DK = Denmark, SE = Sweden, FI = Finland, EST = Estonia, LV = Latvia, LT = Lithuania) (column 2 abbreviations: unconsol. sed. = erodible unconsolidated sedimentary coast, consol. sed. = erodible consolidated sedimentary coast); B. relative glacioisostatic movement. PROG = progradational coast, RETR = retrogradational coast, PROGWAVE = progradational coast with wave driven morphology (see Fig. 1). There are multiple coastal types, types of data and age control methods cited in some of the publications, hence the sum of the papers in categories is greater than the amount of publications altogether.

A		Number of publications							
Country		PL	GER	DK	SE	FI	EST	LV	LT
Coast type	unconsol. sed.	9/2/2	1/-/-	1/-/-	1/-/-		3/-/-	-/1/1	
	consol. sed. resistant rock inland				6/-/11		-/-/1		
Type of data	sedimentological	10/-/-	1/-/-	1/-/-	7/-/10		2/-/1	-/1/1	
	geomorphological	2/-/-		1/-/-	-/-/1		1/-/-		
	geochemical	2/2/2			-/-/8				
	micropalaeontological	5/1/1			1/-/2				
	geophysical			1/-/-	-/-/1				
Age control	varve chronology				5/-/-				
	radionuclides	2/-/-					1/-/-		
	palynology	-/2/2							
	radiocarbon	6/2/2			3/-/11		1/-/1	-/1/1	
	luminescence	1/-/-	1/-/-	1/-/-	-/-/2		1/-/-		
Event	storm	2						1	
	storminess	2			13		1	1	
	MCF	10	1	1	7				

B		Relative glacioisostatic movement		
		PROG	RETR	PROGWAVE
Coast type	unconsol. sed.	3/-/-	11/2/2	1/1/1
	consol. sed. resistant rock inland	5/-/11		1/-/3
	various		1/-/-	
Type of data	sedimentological	7/-/8	8/-/-	2/1/4
	geomorphological	1/-/1	3/-/-	
	geochemical	-/-/8	2/2/2	
	micropalaeontological		5/1/1	1/-/2
	geophysical	-/-/1	1/-/-	
Age control	varve chronology	2/-/-		1/-/-
	radionuclides	1/-/-	2/-/-	
	palynology		-/2/2	
	radiocarbon	3/-/10	6/2/2	1/1/3
	luminescence	2/-/2	2/-/-	
Type of event	storm		2	1
	storminess	11	2	4
	MCF	8	12	2

2.3.2. Marine coastal flooding (MCF)

Coastal flooding is measured in a non-systematic way through existing coastal monitoring networks, including gauge stations, monitoring cameras, satellite-based observations. However, most information about MCF comes from post-event surveys (e.g., Goto et al., 2011; Dominey-Howes, 2020), which involve collecting eyewitness accounts (including video footage), directly documenting the inland extent and depth of flooding (runup height and inundation distance), and assessing morphological, sedimentological, environmental effects, as well as the scale of destruction of coastal infrastructure. This approach was already applied during the November 1872 flooding in Germany and Denmark (Baensch, 1875; Colding, 1881; Clemmensen et al., 2014a).

An indirect method for studying MCF events is remote sensing, particularly through the analysis of satellite and aerial images. Comparing pre- and post-event imagery is especially useful for identifying the extent of flooding. A similar approach is used to analyse morphological changes, employing pre- and post-event mapping

through terrestrial and airborne laser scanning technologies - LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging), which provide rapid, high-resolution topographical data (e.g. Terefenko et al., 2018; Dachenkov and Belov, 2019). The combination of LiDAR data and satellite imagery serves as basis for generating of Digital Elevation Models (DEM) and Digital Terrain Models (DTM), which allow for the assessment of erosion and deposition caused by discrete events.

3. Geographical and topical distribution of research

The research on storms and MCF is unevenly distributed around the Baltic Sea. The main research focus, the objectives and the rationale behind the investigation on past, current and future storms and MCF mimics the most important hazards posed by these phenomena along the discrete stretches of the Baltic Sea coast (Table 4, Table 5). In that respect, the Baltic Sea shoreline can be divided into three main zones: i) the southwestern and southern coast in Sweden, Denmark, Germany and

Table 5

Number of publications on the MCF/storm/storm surges within the instrumental period of research i.e. after 1872, within the Baltic Sea grouped based the: A. country in which the research was undertaken (PL = Poland, GER = Germany, DK = Denmark, SE = Sweden, FI = Finland, EST = Estonia, LV = Latvia, LT = Lithuania) (column 2 abbreviations: unconsol. sed. = erodible unconsolidated sedimentary coast, consol. sed. = erodible consolidated sedimentary coast); B. relative glacioisostatic movement. PROG = progradational coast, RETR = retrogradational coast, PROGWAVE = progradational coast with wave driven morphology (see Fig. 1). There are multiple coastal types and types of cited in some of the publications, hence the sum of the papers in categories is greater than the amount of publications altogether.

A		Number of publications							
Country		PL	GER	DK	SE	FI	EST	LV	LT
Coast type	unconsol. sed.	31/-/7	4/3/8	4/1/3	1/1/2	1/-/1	2/-/1	1/-/2	7/3/6
	consol. sed.				1/-/3				
	resistant rock inland various	3/5/13	4/3/10	-/1/- 1/1/7	4/2/7	-/5/4	-/2/2	-/1/-	-/3/3
Type of data	sedimentological	5/-/-			-/-/1				
	geomorphological	24/1/6	2/-/2	2/2/1			1/-/-		4/2/4
	hydrological	11/5/22	5/7/17	-/2/4	3/4/17	1/3/3	1/3/6	1/-/4	3/5/8
	meteorological	14/5/10	2/6/10	-/3/2	-/3/5	1/3/3	-/4/4	1/2/2	5/6/8
	remote sensing modelling	6/-/- 7/1/2	5/4/13	2/-/1 -/2/5	-/-/4	1/3/3	-/5/5	-/-/1	1/-/-
Type of event	storm	7	7	4	4	5	8	2	6
	storm surge	27	24	10	23	6	10	5	10
	MCF	35	10	5	6	2	2	1	6

B		PROG	RETR	PROGWAVE
Coast type	unconsol. sed.	2/2/2	41/5/21	6/2/4
	unconsol. sed. resistant rock inland various	1/-/3 -/1/- 2/9/9		1/1/6
	sedimentological geomorphological	-/-/1 2/2/-	5/-/- 30/2/12	3/2/1 2/2/6
Type of data	hydrological	3/12/25	17/14/41	2/2/6
	meteorological	-/14/10	8/16/22	5/5/4
	remote sensing		15/-/1	2/-/1
	modelling	1/6/9	10/6/10	-/-/6
Type of event	storm	19	16	4
	storm surge	32	55	14
	MCF	4	47	8

Poland; ii) the eastern part of the Baltic Sea, along the coasts of Gulf of Riga and Gulf of Finland and iii) the Finnish and Swedish coasts of the Bothnian Bay and Swedish coasts of the central Baltic.

The southern and southwestern coasts of the Baltic Sea in southern Sweden, Denmark, Germany and Poland (i) are the most densely populated stretches of the coastline, where the instrumental network has been established the earliest - continuous, although local record starts as early as in the 18th century. This is also the area from which the vast majority of historical sources are available, associated with the activity of the Hanseatic League and the presence of a dense network of ports such as i.e. Lübeck, Stralsund, Greifswald, Kołobrzeg, and Gdańsk. Along the southern and southwestern coasts of the Baltic Sea the major research focus was placed on the hazard posed by extreme storm phenomena to highly urbanized areas and protection measures that may be implemented to defend them. It is the place where the most severe storms within the Baltic Sea associated with MCF have been documented in Denmark and Germany (storms in November 1872 and October 2023). The retrograding, dominant low-lying topography, sandy shorelines with back-barrier wetlands and lakes along these coasts create environments with a relatively high potential for preserving of sedimentary records of MCF events (Fig. 1). These environments have yielded the most detailed sedimentary evidence of past inundations documented so far (e.g., Rotnicki et al., 2016; Piotrowski et al., 2017; Moskalewicz et al., 2020, 2022; Uścińowicz et al., 2020; Leszczyńska et al., 2022). Numerous papers also describe the effects of historical and

most recent storms and MCF on these coasts (Table 3, cf. Supplementary Table 2, e.g.: Bagdanavičiute et al., 2012; Bugajny and Furmańczyk, 2014, 2017, 2020; Furmańczyk and Dudzińska-Nowak, 2009; Furmańczyk et al., 2014; Uścińowicz, Sz., et al., 2004, Uścińowicz, G., et al., 2021) (Table 4, Table 5).

Widespread inland peatlands and alongshore dune fields, which are highly sensitive to wind climate variations driven by North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) variability and associated shifts in storm tracks, serve as valuable archives for reconstructing past changes in storminess. The vast majority of the research and publications on storminess changes over the past 6000 years originate from southern Sweden and the coast of Denmark (Table 4 A, B; Supplementary Table 1; e.g.: Björk and Clemmensen, 2004; de Jong et al., 2006, de Jong, 2007; Bernhardtson et al., 2019; Kylander et al., 2018, 2023).

In the eastern part of the Baltic Sea, along the coasts of Gulf of Riga and Gulf of Finland (ii), the tradition of the storm and MCF research does not extend far into the past and the continuous instrumental record starts in the 19th century CE (Jevrejeva et al., 2001; Johansson et al., 2014). However, the number of publications on this topic has increased rapidly in the 20th and 21st particularly in Estonia and Finland (cf. Supplementary Table 1, 2 and 3). This is due to the rising threat of frequent and intense storms and associated MCF causing changes in the coastal geomorphology. As a result, research has primarily focused on the vulnerability of shorelines to erosion caused by storms and MCF (Table 4, Table 5; Supplementary Table 2, e.g.: Kelpšaitė and Dailidienė,

2011; Jarmalavičius et al., 2012; Jarmalavičius et al., 2016). There is also growing interest in the studying changes in storm intensity and frequency in relation to ongoing climate and sea-level change (Supplementary Table 2, e.g.: Männikus et al., 2020; Kudryavtseva et al., 2021). This research direction is generally supported by research policies and publishing trends.

Along the Finnish and Swedish coasts of the Bothnian Bay and Swedish coasts of the central Baltic (iii) the density of instrumental records on which research on storms can be based is not significant and the record starts only in the 20th century CE (cf. Table 5 A; Supplementary Table 3). With the low risk of extreme storm and destructive MCF events here research focuses on low frequency-high magnitude events such as meteostunamis (Pellikka et al., 2014, 2018, 2020).

4. Storms and marine coastal flooding (MCF) – The state of knowledge for the Baltic Sea

Below we present the state of knowledge on storms and MCF events in the Baltic Sea area based on sedimentary archives, historical sources and instrumental record. For the Baltic Sea, we divide the reconstructed history of storms and MCF into three periods. The longest one spans the time starting with the available geological evidence for storms and MCF and ending with the advent of the historical archives, which is the time of the modern Baltic Sea after the deceleration of Littorina transgression 7000 cal. years BP until ca. 14th century CE. The second period includes events that are documented in historical sources, but took place before the continuous instrumental record has begun. The third period starts with the hydrological and meteorological record of the extreme storm surge of 1872 and includes following events up to now (census year 2024).

The review of the research papers on the topic of storms and MCF was undertaken in Google and GoogleScholar with use of keywords “storms”, “coastal flooding”, “Baltic Sea” with no census date. The reference lists of available research articles were followed in search for

additional papers. Then the research articles were divided into those on the topic of events which took place before the 14th century CE, between the 14th century CE and 1872 and those postdating 1872. The query of historical sources was undertaken in years 2023–2024 in archives of towns at Baltic Sea (Gdańsk, Toruń, Szczecin, Greifswald, Lübeck, Stockholm and Copenhagen). The collections of edited sources and publications in libraries in Toruń, Gdańsk, Berlin and Copenhagen were used. Additionally sources and articles available in Internet collections (Hansischer Geschichtsverein; Internet Archive) were used.

4.1. Timeframe: 7000 cal. years BP – 14th century CE

The advent of the research on prehistoric storms and from sedimentary archives dates back to mid 1990s and the recent decade brought an expansion of interest on that topic. We have found 39 research articles on storms, storminess and MCF based on 5 main types of data, namely: sedimentological, micropalaeontological, geochemical, geomorphological and geophysical (Table 4 A, B; Supplementary Table 1) describing events from the timeframe between 7000 cal. years BP and 14th century CE. These publications usually comprise investigation in one to three study sites or multiple locations within one site.

4.1.1. Storms

There exist extensive geomorphological and sedimentological archives documenting changes in frequency and intensity of storms, i.e. storminess, which come mainly from the eastern and western areas of the Baltic Sea region, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia and Denmark, Sweden, respectively. Longer periods of enhanced storminess within the eastern Baltic Sea region have been identified in the sedimentary record of rhythmic, recurring beach ridges (and coastal scarps) along the uplifting coasts of northern Estonia (Suursaar and Tõnisson, 2017) and the analysis of near-cyclic occurrences of beach/foredune ridges and larger ridge sets within the Tihu ridge plain in Hiiumaa Island (Suursaar et al., 2022). The first record revealed decadal-scale recurrence of enhanced

Fig. 5. Described storminess periods (in black) na periods of frequent marine coastal flooding (MCF, in blue) in the context of positive NAO phases (Olsen et al. 2012) and Holocene Storminess Periods (Sorell et al. 2012). Basemap source: DEM – HELCOM Metadata Catalogue, 2005-07-0. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

storminess within the last 4500 years, with the average periodicity between 23 and 39 years and mean of 31 years (Suursaar and Tõnisson, 2017). The latter archive spans ca. 6000 years and reveals ca. 300 years long intervals of enhanced storminess at 5400–4900, 4800–4500, 4600–4300, 4100–3800, 3700–3400, 3200–2900, 2700–2400, 2200–1900 cal. years BP (Suursaar et al., 2022). The oldest of those enhanced storminess periods, were also detected in coastal lagoon deposits and the foredune ridge set in the Narva-Jõesuu area, in the southeastern coast of the Gulf of Finland (Rosentau et al., 2013). However, the longest record of past storminess from the eastern part of the Baltic Sea spans 8500 years and comes from sedimentary succession recovered from Lake Lilaste in Latvia (Kalińska-Nartiša et al., 2018). It indicates only three peak storminess phases around 7300, 6600–6400 and 6200–6000 cal. years BP with three additional, minor phases between 6000 and 4000 cal. years BP (Fig. 5).

The most detailed reconstructions of storminess from sedimentary archives come from the western part of the Baltic Sea region, from mires of Boarps Mosse and Hyltemossen in south-western Sweden (Björck and Clemmensen, 2004). This succession indicates 27 phases of peak storminess recorded by means of ASI throughout the last 5700 years: 5700–5450, 5200–5100, 4900, 4550, 4200–4100, 3675, 3275, 3050–2850, 2725, 2450, 2300, 2150, 2050, 1950–2000, 1875, 1675, 1450, 1350, 1150, 1100, 1000, 900, 700, cal. years BP (Björck and Clemmensen, 2004) (Fig. 5). Other locations from the western sector of the Baltic Sea, i.e. south-western Sweden, record only a fraction of events identified by Björck and Clemmensen (2004). de Jong et al. (2006) described 6 increased storminess periods at ca. 4800, 4200, 2800–2200, 1500, 1100, 400–50 cal. years BP from a 6500 years long succession of Undarsosse ombrotrophic peat bog (Fig. 5). Multiple punctuating, episodic events of dust deposition dominated by coarse mineral particles interpreted as a sand drift associated with enhanced storminess were also described from south-western Sweden, from Davidsosse bog by Sjöström et al. (2022). These took place at 2800–2130 and 960–360 cal. years BP. The most recent enhanced storminess periods from this part of the Baltic sea region were identified at Anholt Island and are dated for 360 and 100 cal. years BP (Clemmensen et al., 2007).

In all the research from the western part of the Baltic Sea region cited above, periods of increased storminess are likely associated with enhanced winter activity. This contrasts with reconstructions of storminess pattern from the western Jutland Peninsula (Denmark), located just outside the Baltic Sea region, to the south-west of Sweden. There, reconstructions based on ASI from sediment successions in a wetland near the North Sea coast of the Filsø island (Goslin et al., 2018), as well as evidence of coastal dune activity along the western Jutland Peninsula (Clemmensen et al., 2009), suggest an increase in summer storminess. Goslin et al. (2018) identified distinct periods of increased storminess termed the Filsø Storm Periods, occurring approximately 9700–8900, 8700–8400, 8200–7000, 6600–6700, 6400–5300, 5100–4500, 4400–3800, 3300–2900 cal. years BP. Similarly, Clemmensen et al. (2009) documented enhanced storminess phases based on dune field records, dated to approximately 4200, 2800, 1900, 950, and 800 cal. years BP.

When correlating enhanced storminess intervals within the Baltic Sea region with NAO phases a discrepancy is observed. Although there exists a general trend of peak storminess occurring during positive NAO phase and being coupled with southward shift of storm tracks (Sjöström, 2021), the storminess during LIA was frequently associated with negative NAO phase (Clemmensen et al., 2014a). As it is shown on the Fig. 5, the positive NAO phase well reflected in the storminess pattern at all sites occurred between 3000 and 2900 cal. years BP. The enhanced storminess period between 5400 and 4900 cal. years BP (Suursaar et al., 2022; Rosentau et al., 2013) represents a cold climate phase and correlates well with the Holocene maxima of the drift ice in the North Atlantic between 5250 and 5530 cal. years BP (Bond et al., 2001). In the eastern part of the Baltic Sea, the correlation between documented peak

storminess periods as reconstructed by Suursaar et al. (2022) and positive NAO index is more accurate (Fig. 5).

Enhanced storminess periods described by de Jong et al. (2006) and Sjöström et al. (2022) also coincide broadly with the Holocene Storm Period (HSP) III, IV and V of Sorrel et al. (2012) (Fig. 5). However, the timespan of enhanced storminess recorded at each individual research location represent only a fraction of the timespan of discrete HSP. Moreover, some peak storminess events documented by ASI within southern Scandinavia occur outside the HSP. As shown by Kylander et al. (2023) based on research within 4 sites locations spread along a transect of 100 km, there is a difference in proxy and site response to shift in storminess, i.e. not in all locations, the change in storm intensity and frequency is recorded at the same time and with the same intensity. Following from that, in order to compare the discrete storminess records from various sites, it may be useful to apply the modelling of regional storm tracks which reinforces signals common in multiple sites and reduces the influence of random noise (Kylander et al., 2023).

4.1.2. Marine coastal flooding

The evidence of prehistoric MCF events, their frequency and intensity is scarce within the Baltic Sea. Intensive coastal flooding periods were identified by Suursaar and Tõnisson (2017) from northern Estonia. The beach ridge systems described there provide information on the maximum extent of recurrent flooding occurring within the periods of enhanced storminess.

Other examples of sedimentary archives of past MCF were found at the southern Baltic Sea coast in Poland: in Mechelinki (Leszczyńska et al., 2022) and Płutnica Ice Marginal Valley (Uścińowicz et al., 2020) respectively) in the direct vicinity of Puck Lagoon coast, Gulf of Gdańsk (Moskalewicz et al., 2020, 2022) and in Vistula Lagoon (Uścińowicz et al., 2022) (Fig. 5). The record from Mechelinki spans the last 5500 cal. years BP. According to the sedimentary evidence periods of frequent storm-induced MCF occurred from 3600 to 2900 cal. years BP and from 700 cal. years BP to the present. Both periods are characterised by high-frequency of storm surge flooding, in order of 1.3–4.2 events per century. Frequency and landward extent of coastal inundation, largely dependent on the development of beach ridges and aeolian foredunes as natural barriers (Leszczyńska et al., 2022). The record from coastal peatbog of Vistula Lagoon (Uścińowicz, Sz., et al., 2022) showed ten periods of frequent MCF between 7000 and 1500 cal. years BP and record from coastal peatbog of Puck Lagoon (Uścińowicz, Sz., et al., 2020) three such periods. They are interpreted to be associated with cold periods or transitions from cold to warm periods.

Several studies have suggested tsunami-induced MCF events. Mörner (1996, 1999, 2008) and Mörner et al. (2000, Mörner and Dawson, 2011, Mörner et al., 2020) identified evidence for at least sixteen possible tsunami events throughout the Holocene, up until approximately 1000 cal. years BP, associated with post-glacial uplift-induced earthquakes in Scandinavia. The most significant events occurred before 7000 cal. years BP, specifically around 12,400, 11,600, 11,250, 10,430, 9663, and 8600 cal. years BP. Younger potential events, covered in this review, have been dated to approximately 6100, 4000, and 3150 cal. years BP, with the most recent one estimated to have caused a runup height of up to 16.5 m a.s.l. However, some of this evidence has been challenged (Smith and Öhrling, 2022) and may require reevaluation in future research. For instance, while many of these studies propose earthquake-induced landslides as a potential tsunami triggers, detail investigations of such mechanisms in the Baltic Sea are still lacking.

Another possible tsunami-related MCF event was reported by Nikonov (2004) from the Gulf of Finland coast, specifically from Lake Kunda, and broadly dated to the Early Holocene. Additionally, a highly unusual sedimentary succession linked to a high-energy MCF event was extensively documented by Rotnicki et al. (2016) along the southern Baltic coast near Rowy, Poland. Using geophysical surveys, 33 deep boreholes (>10 m), 49 radiocarbon-dated samples, and detailed sedimentological and paleontological analyses, they identified several erosional hollows

filled with thick event deposits composed of redeposited marine sediments. Precise dating of the youngest preserved deposits beneath the event layers, along with overlying gyttja sediments, placed the event at approximately 6600–6630 cal. years BP. While the origin of this event remains uncertain, [Rotnicki et al. \(2016\)](#) considered the possibility of a tsunami generated by a meteorite impact.

4.2. Timeframe: 14th century - 1872

Moving forward along the timescale, into the 14th century and later, the research based on sedimentary archives depicting local effects of storms and MCF can be supplemented with information from written historical sources.

4.2.1. Storms

The overview of 62 storms described in chronicles and annals between the beginning of the 14th and the end of the 18th century is presented in [Table 2](#). Eighty storms have been documented in detail in Hanseatic records and correspondence, as published in the ‘Hanseresse’ compilation and documents featured in the ‘Hanseatisches Urkundenbuch’ spanning the time between the beginning of the 14th to the end of the 15th century CE ([Table 3](#)). Additional notices (ca. 30) are taken from sources such as Lübeckisches Urkundenbuch, Mecklenburgisches Urkundenbuch or Liv- Est- und Kurländisches Urkundenbuch. The prevalence of these records comes from the 15th and 17th centuries (24 and 17 respectively), while fewer instances are noted in the 14th, 16th and 18th centuries (6, 8 and 6 respectively). This discrepancy might be caused by a smaller number of chronicles, being the major source of historical knowledge on storms, dated to the 14th century. However, this can also be a piece of evidence for climate change during the specified periods.

Despite extensive data collected from historical sources, it is difficult to identify any trend in the frequency of storms based on these accounts only. Such analyses, if feasible, are limited to the most severe events in the Baltic. However, when examining historical data from the early 14th to the late 18th century CE, there are years with no remarks on storms whatsoever ([Table 2 and 3](#)). In the best studied period up to 1500, storm frequency peaks in 1492 with six events, followed by 1484 with five (potentially all descriptions referring to a single storm), and four each for 1482 and 1486. Three storms are noted for 1393, 1428, 1436 (possibly a single storm is described in two independent sources), 1472 (with one storm potentially described in two types of sources), 1477 (a potential duplicate), 1490, 1491, and 1493. The storm of September 1497 is mentioned in both narrative sources and an exceptionally numerous array of chronicles, as well as administrative sources and numerous correspondences.

Notably, there are very detailed descriptions of storms by Curicke (1610–1667). He listed storms occurring in 1361, 1465, 1482, 1486, 1497, 1515, and 1616. Some copies of this chronicle have annotations in the margins about subsequent storms added by readers and owners of such a copy. The storms that were added there occurred in 1675, 1737, and 1747, but these mentions are primarily related to the damage that those storms caused to some church buildings. Thus, a total of 10 storms are noted in this source spanning from the 14th to the mid-18th century, encompassing later additions. Curicke referred to authors such as Caspar Schütz (*Historia Rerum Prussicarum*) and Henneberger (*Erclerung der Preussischen grössern Landtaffel*), however the list presented in his account is not complete. Other chronicles document more storms, with some well-documented events described in additional twenty sources.

Attempts to correlate storm events described in chronicles with information from administrative sources reveal the inadequacy of compilations reliant on only one type of source. Even if assumed that chronicles, being the most reliable source of information on storms, mention only severe events, they only account for over a quarter of all storms mentioned in other sources.

The analysis of the monthly distribution of storms documented in

historical sources was based on Hanseatic administrative sources and narrative sources separately ([Fig. 6A, B](#)). In the case of Hanseatic correspondence, the highest number of storms was identified in July, October and November ([Fig. 6A](#)). While the count for storms recorded in these months may have been higher, precise dating for some remains unclear, and they can only be determined to have occurred in the autumn. While comparing this data to instrumental record, it is nonetheless clear that the pattern is different ([Fig. 6](#)). The large number of storms in the warm part of the year from historical sources ([Fig. 6A, B](#)) is an artefact of the duration of the shipping season and does not reflect the natural occurrence of these events. In the historical sources associated with the shipping mainly the storms which influenced the freight are reported. During the winter the amount of ships operating on the sea was much smaller, mainly due to weather and ice conditions on the sea.

The reconstructions based on sedimentary archives from the period between the 14th century and 1872 do not depict discrete storm events, however they reflect general changes in storminess. Within the timespan between 14th and the 2nd half of the 19th century, based on ASI, [Björck and Clemmensen \(2004\)](#) reconstruct peak storminess periods at 475, 400, 300 and 130 cal. years BP, what is respectively the 2nd half of the 15th, mid of 16th, mid of 17th and 1st half of the 19th century. The enhanced storminess from the Little Ice Age has also been reconstructed based on the evolution of high non-continuous dune belt along the Estonian coast ([Tõnisson et al., 2020](#)) and from the ridge-swale beach system at Tihu ridge, Estonia ([Suursaar et al., 2022](#)). Comparison of sedimentary archives with historical sources shows that the enhanced storminess periods in the 15th and 17th century CE is well depicted within both types of archives.

4.2.2. Marine coastal flooding

The review of the research on MCF events within the timeframe between 14th century and 1872 reveals great difficulty in comparison, compilation and correlation of both types of archives namely sedimentary and historical. This is associated with subjective character of descriptions and inaccurate dating of storm and MCF events in administrative and narrative sources on one hand, and difficulty in precise dating of these events from sedimentary archives.

One of the best documented, severe MCF events described in numerous chronicles, administrative sources and correspondence took place in September 1497. The historical descriptions of this event have been reviewed by [Riemann \(1873\)](#), [Szultka \(2000\)](#), and recently subjected to detail comparative analysis by [Piotrowski et al. \(2024\)](#), who verified the historical description against archeological. Topographical and geological data for the city of Kołobrzeg (Kolberg). The analysed sources report damage to ships in Ribnitz, Stralsund, Bukowo Morskie and Koszalin as well as to harbors in Gdańsk, Elbląg and Kaliningrad. The extreme storm surge flooded coastal cities, towns and their infrastructure such as for example the Carthusian monastery in Darłowo. Marine inundation caused topographical changes in the area of Łeba, Kołobrzeg and Vistula Spit. There are also accounts reporting inland influence of wind associated with 1497 storm as evidenced by descriptions of damage to Braniewo and the Chełmno land, as well as damages in Darłowo ([Piotrowski, 2007](#); [Piotrowski et al., 2024](#)).

Sedimentary archives of major MCF event in 1497 has been identified at sites along the southern Baltic Sea coast, both onshore ([Piotrowski et al., 2017](#)) and offshore ([Szczęśniak et al., 2023](#)). The most extensive documentation was provided by [Piotrowski et al. \(2017\)](#), who conducted detailed geological investigations on a large coastal wetland in Rogowo, near the mouth of the Rega River. Their study included 198 drillings, four trenches, grain-size analysis, micropaleontological and geochemical examinations, and 28 radiocarbon dates. They identified a distinct sand layer within peat sequence, characterised by an erosional lower boundary, a thickness ranging from a few centimeters to several tens of centimeters, and inland extent of over 1200 m. The characteristics of this layer resemble typical tsunami deposits (e.g., [Morton et al., 2007](#)), suggesting that, without precise age control and historical data,

Fig. 6. Monthly distribution of storms. A. Hanserecesse and Hansisches Urkundenbuch 1876–1916 from about 1350 to 1500; B. Narration sources from 1300 to 1800. C.-F. Period 1960–2020 (Wolski and Wiśniewski, 2023). C. Wismar; D. Władysławowo; E. Parnu; F. Kemi; G. Annual number of storm surges in the Baltic Sea for the period 1960–2010 (Wolski et al., 2016).

Fig. 7. Frequencies (numbers) of sedimentary, geophysical, geochemical, micropalaeontological, hydrological, meteorological, geomorphological, remote sensing, and numerical modelling studies for various time periods and years of publication. Numbers on the right and the left of each row give the total number of papers for each time period used in this study.

distinguishing extensive storm-induced coastal flooding from tsunami events can be challenging. This deposit is the most extensive event layer recorded in the region over at least the past 2000 years—since the onset of wetland accumulation and sea-level stabilization—indicating that the storm on September 17, 1497, and its associated flooding were likely among the most severe in Baltic history.

Piotrowski et al. (2017) also identified a thinner, less extensive sand layer from the 18th century, preserved only locally. Its origin was analysed in the context of historical reports (Brüggemann, 1779; Galczyńska, 2001; Piotrowski, 2007), which describe large storms, including the so-called “der Seebär” (“the Sea Bear”) flooding of 1757 CE. This event was described in a manner resembling a tsunami or meteotsunami. However, due to dating uncertainties, it is not possible to conclusively link the sand layer to a specific storm or tsunami-like event.

The information on the number of MCF events between 14th and 19th century gathered from sedimentary archives around Gulf of Gdańsk allows to indicate the periods of more frequent flooding, which took place between 15th and the 18th century during the cold period of the Little Ice Age (Uściniowicz et al., 2020; Moskalewicz et al., 2020). The sandy storm deposits identified by Moskalewicz et al. (2020) along the coast of Gulf of Gdańsk, are most likely correlated with storms in 1825, 1872 and 1914. However unequivocal evidence for the correlation of these deposits with cited events lacks, due to uncertainty of dating. Within Puck Bay, Leszczyńska et al. (2022) based on sedimentary archives of sandy layers within otherwise organic rich succession, identifies the period of frequent MCF events to the last 700 cal. years BP years with no direct references to specific events.

4.3. Timeframe: 1872 - present

There exist great wealth of information on storms and MCF events within the instrumental timeframe. When considering the research on storms based solely on instrumental records 189 articles citing 5 main types of data, namely hydrological, meteorological, geomorphological, remote sensing, and numerical modelling, what results in 321 different combinations of approaches to the research on storms and MCF in the instrumental record timespan (Fig. 7; Supplementary Table 1 and 2). There is a remarkable increase in the number of publications only from the year 1995 CE onward with the highest number of 92 publications for the period of past five years (2020–2024). A large number of publications covers hydrological measurements (36 %) followed by meteorological (24 %) and numerical modelling studies (21.5 %). Geomorphological studies comprise 12.5 % and geospatial studies

(remote sensing and digital elevation models, DEM) 6 %. Storm related articles dealing with the southern, western and eastern parts of the Baltic Sea coast comprise 69 % while only 12 % focus on the central and northern coasts and 19 % cover the entire Baltic Sea, often from a global or European perspective. The publications concentrate on topics of storm frequency, sea-level states, including storm surge levels during storms and wave heights, as well as modelling studies of sea-levels during storms and storm surges in the instrumental record time.

4.3.1. Storms

The earliest storm event instrumentally documented, but also widely acknowledged in historical sources and documented from sedimentary archives within the Baltic Sea region is the storm in November 1872. A book by Aakjær and Buch (2022) summarizes the vast amount of information on the damage caused by MCF induced by the November 1872 storm published inter alia in contemporary journals (Illustrierte Zeitung 1872) and official reports (Quade, 1872; Anonymous, 1872; Aakjær and Buch, 2022; Bork et al., 2022). During this event more than 300 people along the German, Danish and Swedish coast died, including 127 at sea (Fredericksson et al., 2017; Kiecksee, 1972). The damage reported included not only port infrastructure, but also houses and public infrastructure in towns and cities (i.e. Bornholm, Lolland and Falster). There are also official Danish Royal documents giving honorary awards to heroes involved in e.g. rescue operations during and after the storm (Aakjær and Buch, 2022).

The meteorological and hydrological setting of this event in Germany and Denmark was the subject of one of the earliest systematic instrumental research published in scientific literature, in which the storm surge levels and the weather set-up (Baensch, 1875; Colding, 1881; Petersen, 1924) were analysed in detail. The preconditions of the extreme character of this event was the persistent westerly wind occurring between the 1st and the 10th of November, caused by stable low-pressure system over Scandinavia. The persistent westerly wind pushed away seawater to the eastern part of the Baltic Sea and allowed the inflow of water from the North Sea and the Atlantic Ocean (storm weather scenario i, section 1.3.2). After the 10th of November, low-pressure over Scandinavia was substituted by a high-pressure centre coupled with low-pressure centre over central Europe. This changed the major direction of wind from westerly to northeasterly with the extreme wind force (Baensch, 1875; Colding, 1881 after Rodloff, 1972). The above reconstruction was revisited within the project MUSTOK (modelling of extreme storm surges on the German coastline; Jensen, 2009; Jensen et al., 2009). Bork and Müller-Navarra (2009) modelled

hydrological conditions during the 1872 storm based on measurements. They concluded that even the small change in the force, direction, spatial extent and temporal evolution may amplify the storm-induced sea-levels from high to extremely high. Later Bork et al. (2022) reported that natural oscillations and filling of the Baltic Sea played a minor role in evolution of the excessive water elevations during the 1872 storm. The offshore topography, combined with the restricted outflow of water through Belts and the Sound were the major cause the extreme sea-levels (Bork et al., 2022).

The maximum sea-level during 1872 storm was estimated based on the instrumental record for 3.14 to 3.29 m a.s.l. at Travemünde (Jensen et al., 2022). Based on sedimentary archives in form of an extensive beach ridge and a number of washover fans spreading along the Danish coast the sea-level during that storm was estimated to reach up to 2.8 m a.s.l. (Clemmensen et al., 2014b). Until today water levels of all following extreme storms were ca. 1 m below that (Hofstede and Hamann, 2022; Perlet-Markus, 2023). The fact that, in the context of instrumental measurements, the 1872 storm may be classified as outlier, poses a problem in determination of water level exceedance probabilities. Return period of such an event as 1872 storm calculated using various methodologies vary from ca. 180–200 years to more than 10000 years (Jensen and Töppe, 1990) and is cited by Fredericksson et al. (2016) to be unrealistically low. However, Mudersbach and Jensen (2009) prove, that approach of integrated extreme value statistics in which observed, historical and modelled data are combined, give appropriate predictions of probability, as the 1872 is not an outlier within the context of such an extended dataset. When combining the three sources of data, namely, observed, historical and modelling, into extreme values statistics, the return period shortens from 10,000 years to 3400 years (Mudersbach and Jensen, 2009).

One of the first modern reanalysis of meteorological set-up of the 1872 storm was undertaken by Rosenhagen and Bork (2009). They performed a high resolution analysis of the grid values of the wind vector and air pressure for the Baltic Sea at the time of the event, before and after. They concluded that water levels as observed, compare with high accuracy with simulations based on reconstructed wind vector field from air pressure data. Later, Feuchter et al. (2013) traced the 1872 storm event in the “Twentieth Century Reanalysis” (20CR) dataset, which comprises six-hourly, 3-dimensional, global atmospheric data back in time to 1871. They concluded that the evolution of the storm events is well depicted in the 20CR data, but its strength is underestimated.

Other examples of the early hydrological and meteorological case studies of instrumentally recorded storms comprise events which took place along the Swedish coast in 1914 (Ljungdahl, 1921) and 1921 (Weibull and Svantesson, 1924). The work by Ljungdahl (1921) comprises multiple tables with sea-level measurements, drawings of sea-level oscillations and synoptic situation. The publication by Weibull and Svantesson (1924) is well illustrated with photographs and hand drawings of coastal changes following the storm.

Later, with the rising amount of systematic instrumental measurements catalogues of storms and storm surge levels giving insights into storm-induced sea-level change combined with the meteorological set-up were published for selected stretches of the Baltic Sea coast. One of the early comprehensive catalogues was compiled by Majewski et al. (1983), presented observations from 5 gauge stations along Polish and German coast and comprised one of the first attempt to unify the definitions of the storm surge. Majewski et al. (1983) used the reference value of 500 cm for mean sea-level and defined the storm surge as a rise of water level above 570 cm for the Polish and 590 cm for German stretch of the Baltic coast. Later, Sztobryn et al. (2005) in yet another catalogue of storm events put forward the threshold for storm events at the level of 600 cm. In the early 2000' other catalogues primarily focused on presentation of maximum sea-level states during storm surges comprised inter alia work by Hupfer et al. (2003) for German coast and by Olsson (2002) for Swedish coast.

After these early compilations, more comprehensive overviews of the storm-induced sea-level were published, supplemented with the statistical analyses of annual distribution of storm-induced extreme water levels, their trends or probability of occurrence. An important contribution to analysis of the extreme sea-levels during storm surges within the whole Baltic Sea was a series of papers by Wolski et al. (2014, 2016) and Wolski and Wiśniewski (2020, 2021, 2023) covering the time period 1960 to 2020 with the evaluation of tide-gauge data from several stations around the Baltic Sea coast. Based on the data from 1960 to 2010 Wolski and Wiśniewski (2020) and Wolski et al. (2016) show that the highest number of storms and extreme sea-levels associated with storm surges (Fig. 6G) were most frequent and lasted the longest within the inland ends of the great bays, along the north-eastern and eastern coasts of the Gulf of Finland, Riga and Bothnian Bay. Between 1960 and 2020, the height of maximum sea-levels has increased, on average with a trend value of 0.28 cm per year (on average from 95 to 111 cm). Also the duration of high sea-levels associated with storm surges within the Baltic Sea has increased by a third (Wolski and Wiśniewski, 2021). Moreover, the probability of occurrence of high sea-level, including storm-induced events has been reported to increase within the few last decades for multiple stretches of the Baltic Sea coast: eastern Baltic including the Gulf of Riga (Kudryavtseva et al., 2021) and specifically Lithuania (Dailidienė et al., 2006), Latvia and Estonia (Valdmann et al., 2008; Soomere and Pindsoo, 2016; Suursaar and Sooäär, 2007), northern coast of the central Baltic (Broman et al., 2006; Kudryavtseva et al., 2021) and the Finnish coast of Bothnian Bay and Gulf of Finland (Pellikka et al., 2018).

The sea-level, including the sea-level associated with storm surges can be projected into the past (or future) based on modelling studies. Within the Baltic Sea research works showing that in particular high resolution local models predict sea-level states with satisfactory accuracy. Novotny et al., (2006) model observed sea-level variations, including storm surges with an accuracy of 5 to 9 cm and 8 cm for long-term variations (>2 months). Gräwe and Burchard (2012), conducted 100-year model experiments for the western Baltic sea with control runs for the period between 1960 and 2000. They showed that there is a linear trend dependence between storm-surge level and the mean sea-level, furthermore that the sea-level has greater potential to increase storm-surge levels than increased wind speed.

The described changes in the extreme sea-levels caused by storms are hypothesised to be caused by western circulation that has been intensifying through the late 20th and early 21st centuries and the rising global mean sea-level (GMSL), both associated with global warming processes (Wolski and Wiśniewski, 2021). Additionally, the recent research shows that increasing frequency of cyclones clustering (Post and Köuts, 2014), combined with the change in their trajectory in relation to specific site (Averkiew and Klevanny, 2007; Averkiew and Klevanny, 2010) rise the probability of the extreme storm-induced sea-levels.

In contrast to observed increase in storm-induced extreme sea-levels and the probability of their occurrence, the trends in the number of storms within the last few decades are inconclusive for the area of the Baltic Sea. The statistical analysis of the number of storms within the whole Baltic Sea indicates that their number is increasing steadily for the last 60 years from 3.1 to 5.5 per year (Wolski et al., 2014; Wolski and Wiśniewski, 2021). However, the regional approach to storm frequency analysis reveals differences in storminess changes within various parts of the sea. The highest increase in the number of storms per year took place in Gulf of Finland (from 5.5 to 11.5 per year), the western Baltic area (from 4.0 to 7.1 per year), and Bothnian Bay at Kemi (from 4.8 to 9.7 per year). Along the southern Baltic Sea coast the increase is from 1.7 to 3.3 storms per year (Wolski and Wiśniewski, 2021). A similar trend is depicted by Filipiak and Malinowska (2016) for the south-western and southern and Dailidienė et al. (2006, 2012) and Johansson et al. (2014) for the eastern part of the Baltic Sea. Moreover, in the eastern sector of the sea, there is observed increase in storm duration associated with

concomitant change of the major wind direction, but not wind speed (Soomere and Pindsoo, 2016). On the contrary, the data for western (north Denmark) (Clemmensen et al., 2014a) and the northern part of the Baltic shows that storm frequency is generally decreasing, however the proportion of severe storms, is slightly increasing (Arra, 2018).

A separate topic of investigation is the research on mean and maximum wave height associated with storms. This research shows that although the maximum and mean wave height associated with storms has not been significantly altered throughout the instrumental record period, there are some regional discrepancies. Within the southwestern part of the Baltic Sea there is a linear rising trend in the average wave height of 1.8 % per year following the variation in wind speed during storms (Broman et al., 2006). Additionally, in this part of the Baltic Sea, changes in wind direction cause a change in wave run-up and following from that their erosional and depositional potential. Adell et al. (2023) indicates that along the southern coasts of Sweden, there is a gradual increase in the wave energy exposure from west to east and wave direction is correlated to NAO phase, with the strongest and highest waves being associated with the positive NAO. Additionally, positive high correlation coefficient of ≥ 0.5 for the NAO index, the maximum significant wave height and the number of storms for Baltic Proper were identified for the period 1980–2015. A variability period of about 10–12 years was identified (Myslenkov et al., 2018). On the contrary the research on the south-eastern sector of the Baltic Sea (mainly Lithuanian coast) indicates that there are considerable inter-annual changes in mean and maximum wave height, but there are no statistically significant trends (Kelpšaitė and Dailidienė, 2011). By comparing the mean and extreme wave associated with storm data from south-eastern part of the Baltic Sea with those from the northern part it can be concluded that short term variations of the annual mean wave height have a similar pattern at all sites, although the decadal and sub-decadal variability is different (Kelpšaitė et al., 2008).

An important aspect of storm reporting is the number of fatalities associated with an event. In various sources the information is available on loss of life at sea due to vessels sinking during severe storms (Supplementary Table 4). 35 fatalities were recorded in maritime accidents in the Baltic Sea between 2011 and 2022 (Eurostat 2024), at least in part as a result of storms. Most infamous storm-induced accidents involved the ferries MS *Jan Heweliusz* in 1993 (55 fatalities) and MS *Estonia* a year later (852 fatalities).

4.3.2. Marine coastal flooding (MCF)

The 1872 CE storm-induced MCF also left a record in coastal sediments, such as in the Gulf of Gdańsk, where Moskalewicz et al. (2020) documented sand layers with an erosional, sharp lower boundary attributed to this event, as well as to a slightly younger major storm in 1914 CE. Interestingly, they observed that none of the historical storm

events over the past 100 years have produced a distinguishable sedimentary record in the same wetland environments. These findings highlight the importance of incorporating geological evidence into risk models and storm return period predictions, which are often based solely on instrumental measurements.

Various remote sensing techniques allow to assess for instance the morphological changes of the shoreline cause by MCF events (Dachenkov and Belov, 2019; Giza et al., 2021; Łysko et al., 2023; Hansen et al., 2021; Terefenko et al., 2018, 2024a) or volumetric amounts of the sediment eroded and/or accumulated during MCF events (Dudzińska-Nowak and Wężyk, 2014; Eelsalu et al., 2022; Terefenko et al., 2024b). All these research centres on the south-western, southern and eastern stretches of the Baltic Sea shoreline. They unequivocally indicate that the erosion could be positively correlated with the number of storm events and sea-water level rise associated with storm surges (Dudzińska-Nowak and Wężyk, 2014; Dachenkov and Belov, 2019). It is shown that high frequency of storm events prevent the coastal zone from recovering and rises the susceptibility of a coast to further erosion. The waves associated with following storms and storm surges attack directly the cliff and beaches enhancing the erosion (Terefenko et al., 2018). Detailed quantifications of the sediment budget however, allow to infer that regular changes of the wind direction, associated with regular weather patterns aid to maintain the beach and recover after the storm (Eelsalu et al., 2022). Giza et al. (2021) indicates, that the changes in landcover of the coastal areas also influence resistance of the coast to storm-induced MCF erosion.

In the northern part of the Baltic Sea, recently, the research on meteotsunami-induced MCF have been intensified. There, meteotsunami has been documented in the Bothnian Bay, along the Finnish coastline (Pellikka et al., 2014, 2018, 2020). Eyewitness report sea-level variations up to 1.5 m a.m.s.l., but oscillations recorded by tide-gauges are considerably smaller, ca. 30 cm (Pellikka et al., 2014). The meteotsunamis are rapid events with several oscillations lasting for ca. 5 to 15 mins.

Paprotny et al. (2023, 2024) compiled information on 2521 floods in 42 European countries which caused significant socioeconomic impacts, including 99 of coastal and 45 of compound (co-occurring coastal and riverine flooding) type. Of these, 16 coastal flood originated from storm surges in the Baltic Sea and/or the Danish Straits. The events are listed in Supplementary Table 4, indicating their date, location, reported impacts, and associated literature. The list is not complete, as it excludes events which took place in countries under Soviet Union control, for instance: in October 1967 in Estonia and Latvia, November 1969 in Latvia, and January 1983 in Lithuania (European Environment Agency, 2024b; Estonian Environment Agency, 2024a; Öhtuleht, 2020; Kudryavtseva et al., 2021; Jauns.lv, 2022). The latter storm is known to have caused a major flood in Poland.

Fig. 8. The timespan encompassed by discrete research methods applied in research on marine coastal flooding (MCF).

5. Combining instrumental record, historical and sedimentary archives of storms and MCF – Advantages and pitfalls

The three types of records available for the investigation of storms and MCF events differ in time-span, geographical range, resolution, accuracy and continuity (Fig. 7, 8). Sedimentary archives are the only ones that give insight into the far past of the storms and MCF events history, even a few thousands of years before the advent of historical sources and instrumental records. They mostly record MCF events, with underrepresentation of storms that did not cause flooding. These repositories are limited in geographical range and record local changes in sedimentary setting, geomorphology, and ecological conditions, caused by these phenomena. A variety of sedimentary proxies allows the reconstruction of detailed picture of the event and gives a view of environmental consequences of these phenomena. Sedimentary archives picture only the most severe events, therefore they are not continuous and are of low temporal resolution. They are prone to post depositional changes or stacking of evidence for consecutive MCF events.

The frequency of strong wind associated with storms is reflected by sedimentary evidence of storminess in the form of aeolian mineral matter input in mostly organic successions or geomorphological evidence presented by beach ridges or dunes.

Most of the historical records come from densely populated areas of the southern and western Baltic Sea, which have been urbanized for few centuries and became local maritime transport and trade centers. The historical archives, being important supplementary sources of information pushing the knowledge on storms from instrumental record back in time often suffer from subjectivity. Very rarely the parameters of storms or MCF are precisely indicated, which jeopardizes the exact description of the event. They picture in detail some aspects and consequences of the most severe events, the ones that are most important from the anthropogenic point of view. For instance, the information about storms in Hanseatic correspondence and documents was associated with the damage caused by these events in maritime transportation and losses of goods. Following from that the amount of storm events in discrete months may not only reflect the weather conditions, but it may also be the artefact of seasonality of maritime transportation as the intensity of Baltic travel was intrinsically tied to the seasons (Fig. 6). During winter months, travel would often be suspended due to the presence of ice at sea, significantly affecting the provided statistics on the amount of storms in discrete months. In this context, a synthesis focusing on the most severe storms, typically documented in chronicles, which considered not only the damage to ships but also the damage caused at the coast, is more reliable. Particularly useful are sources that describe events taking place during the instrumental record times such as 1872 storm event as the comparison of historical descriptions and instrumental data allows to set a scale to similar events known only from written archives, for which the measurements do not exist.

The instrumental record based on meteorological and hydrological measurements is limited to the last ca. 200 years. Additionally, each of the observations is geographically restricted, representing local conditions. At the beginning, instrumental record was based on low frequency observations. With time and technical progress its continuity, reliability and precision grew. Currently, it potentially presents with the highest accuracy and timely resolution. Similarly, the geographical coverage of the measurements changed with time. The network of instrumental records of various parameters of sea state and weather throughout the Baltic Sea grows rapidly. The changes in geographical and timely resolution of the instrumental data limit the comparability of the observations from the past and present. However, the instrumental observations, are invaluable sources of information, providing a benchmark for comparison between various storms and MCF events from the past and present. It delivers the data for testing environmental consequences of events of various scales. Additionally, it serves as an input for modelling studies.

The incorporation of all three types of evidence for past storms and

MCF in particular to analysis of events, which took place within the last 200 years allows the calibration of all the types against each other. The instrumental record, providing objective data allows to put subjective historical descriptions into unbiased background. Similarly, the analysis of sedimentary and geomorphic traces of contemporary measured storm-induced MCF allows better understanding of depositional processes operating during storm-induced MCF and resulting sedimentary archives – their evolution and preservation. Additionally, observations of post-depositional alterations of sedimentary archives allows separation of original evidence for storm or MCF from following environmental influence. Moreover, the integration of sedimentary, historical and instrumental pieces of evidence on storms and MCF into the modelling approach allows potentially to develop reconstructions of past events or predictive models for the future.

6. Impact of storms and MCF events on different coastal settings around the Baltic Sea

Monitoring and description of impact of storms or MCF events on discrete types of the coast is based on several basic methodological assumptions, i.e. (i) analysis of changes in the position of the shoreline and/or dune base using archival cartographic material (Bagdanaviciute et al., 2012; Deng et al., 2017), as well as more recent digital terrain models [DTM] data (Hansen et al., 2021; Uścińowicz and Szarafin, 2018), (ii) geodetic measurements of the beach and foredune profile (Jarmalavičius et al., 2016; Szmytkiewicz et al., 2018), (iii) implementation of multi-temporal models based on DTMs (Michałowska and Głowienka, 2022), as well as combinations of the above methods supplemented by fundamental studies such as geomorphological and geological mapping, (iv) tracing sediment influx (Tysiąg et al., in review).

The susceptibility of any coast to erosion associated with storms or MCF probability do not increase linearly and uniformly for all stretches of the coastline around the Baltic Sea (Suursaar et al., 2002; Musielak et al., 2017; Almar et al., 2021; Uścińowicz et al., 2024). Within the Baltic Sea the most susceptible to erosional activity of storms and to hazards associated with MCF are erodible unconsolidated sedimentary coast (type i), located along the retrograding, southwest, south and southeast coasts. Additionally to natural susceptibility to erosion and re-shaping by storms and MCF events, these areas remain under constant stress associated with retrograding character of the coast. Moreover contemporary climatic changes in particular recently intensified western circulation, increasing frequency of cyclones clustering causing extreme storms, and rising global mean sea-level has put stretches along Gulf of Riga and Gulf of Finland in particular severe threat of storms and MCF. In the near future these shorelines are predicted to face significant changes.

Along the low elevated topography beach and coastal meadows shoreline of the coast type (i) i.e. erodible unconsolidated sedimentary coast, MCF events have the most widespread impact through erosion of the nearshore, beach and foredunes, but also of entire low and narrow spits, which are easily disrupted during storms. In most cases, the effects of such erosion are reversible by rebuilding the beach and dunes during calm seasons. However, relatively permanent effects of storm erosion can occur in so-called 'hot spot' areas, the persistence of which depend on a number of factors (Galano, 2007; Kraus and Galano, 2001; Uścińowicz et al., 2024). Due to re-shaping of the near shore, beach and beach barrier, the low-lying areas of the barrier's hinterland, also those associated with wide barriers with high dune systems are then at high risk of MCF (Sitkiewicz et al., 2020).

The changes caused by consecutive storms along the erodible rock coast (type (ii)) are more spectacular, often in the form of extensive landslides, than in the case of the open sandy low coasts. This is confirmed by the extensive literature on cliff studies (Dudzińska-Nowak and Wężyk, 2014; Gunther and Thiel, 2009; Orviku et al., 2013; Terfenko et al., 2018; Uścińowicz et al., 2019a, 2019b). However, the

effect of these processes on the coastline is of lesser significance (Uściniowicz et al., 2014). Steep coasts made up of poorly consolidated rocks, such as Cretaceous carbonate sediments (chalk), Neogene low-lithified sands with interbedded lignite, Pleistocene glacial deposits and even Holocene peats, are a more effective obstacle than the barrier coasts. Nevertheless, they also experience erosive effects of prolonged or repeated storms, storm surges and MCF. This is not a simple relationship that can be described by a 'marine erosion - coastal retreat' scheme. Often the geological structure and associated hydrogeological conditions are dominant for these coasts - groundwater in hydraulic connection with marine water (Lidzbarski and Tarnawska, 2015) may be the main erosion factor.

The resistant rock coasts (type (iii)) have received little attention in the literature associated with the Baltic Sea and with regard to storm or MCF induced geomorphological changes. The resistant rock coast is least sensitive to erosional effects exerted by consecutive storms of MCF events. Moreover, this type of the coast occupy mostly shoreline stretches in the uplifting northern region of the sea.

In a broad review of the literature on the subject of susceptibility of discrete types of the coast, it should be noted that it is becoming increasingly clear that the understanding of processes occurring in the terrestrial part of the coastal zone cannot be achieved without understanding the factors located in the nearshore and offshore part of the coastal zone, e.g. bottom morphology, geological structure, hydrodynamic conditions, etc. (Averes et al., 2021; Orviku et al., 2013; Terfenko et al., 2020; Uściniowicz et al., 2021). It is also significant that morphological data collected over many years, and more recently high temporal resolution data, are being subjected to advanced analytical methods (Łysko et al., 2023; Terfenko et al., 2019; Moskalewicz et al., 2024; Tysiąg et al., in review).

7. Ongoing and predicted change in storms and MCF at the background of the climate change

The modelling of future storm frequency is not straightforward as the Baltic Sea basin lies in the transitional zone between oceanic and continental climates. The response of such transitional zones to global climate change is ambiguous. Additionally, wind climate projections are uncertain, due to differences in atmospheric circulation between discrete models (HELCOM, 2021).

The Baltic Sea region lies between two provinces delimited for the purpose of climatic modelling: central and northern Europe. For central Europe (the southern and eastern sector of the Baltic Sea), storm frequency and intensity is predicted to increase (Pinto and Raible, 2012; Donat et al., 2011; Beniston et al., 2007; Feser et al., 2015; Harvey et al., 2020). For the northern and eastern Europe the evaluation of future frequency and intensity of storms, cyclones and high-impact wind speed is inconclusive. It is predicted though that the storm track, together with NAO circulation will most probably move towards northeast (Mölter et al., 2016). For northern Europe there is a predicted decrease in storm frequency (Karremann et al., 2014; Beersma et al., 1997) but an increase in storm intensity (Pinto and Raible, 2012; Donat et al., 2010).

The storminess record based on the last decades of instrumental measurements indicates with high confidence that storms are related to intense zonal circulation, i.e. shifts of the westerlies. Available data for the past decades indicate that the trends in the number of storms and following storm surges are inconclusive for the area of the Baltic Sea and the influence of the large-scale circulation on the storm frequency is not well understood, with strong inter-annual to multidecadal variability (Bärring and Fortuniak, 2009; Myslenkov et al., 2018; HELCOM, 2021; Rutgersson et al., 2015; Uściniowicz et al., 2024). Based on research by Myslenkov et al. (2018), Arra (2018) and NCAR (2024), the positive trend in NAO indices is related to more frequent storms. This is contrary to Björck and Clemmensen (2004) and Clemmensen et al. (2015), who connect the intensive storminess during LIA and the 19th century CE to negative NAO indices at sites just outside of the direct Baltic Sea area.

This contrast and instability with time may imply interplay of various storminess driving mechanisms comprising NAO (e.g., Sjöström, 2021) phased with extra regional circulation pattern of Western Europe Pressure Anomaly (cf. Masselink et al., 2023; Scott et al., 2021).

Simultaneously, a positive trend in the amount of deep low pressure centres/cyclones for the last 60 years has been observed (Rutgersson et al., 2022). However, while reviewing statistical analyses of the time-sequences of climatic data, it needs to be taken into account that the trend depends on the timespan analysed (Rutgersson et al., 2022; Uściniowicz et al., 2024).

Detailed climate modelling of future storm weather conditions undertaken by Mäll et al. (2020) for IPCC RCP 4.5 and 8.5 CO₂ emission scenarios indicates that the area of low atmospheric pressure influencing the circulation over the Baltic Sea will grow in size. Subsequently, the meridional zone of strong wind will be pushed towards the south and the peak wind speed will increase. This wind speed increase will take place in autumn months, which is usual storm season within the Baltic Sea (HELCOM, 2021). At the same time, the duration of the storm will increase, and the direction of the wind will rotate (Soomere and Pindsoo, 2016). In the eastern part of the Baltic Sea, this will yield an increase in surge heights and a change in the direction of waves approaching the coast. Along the southern Baltic Sea coast, on the contrary, this weather set-up will increase the frequency and probability of the seiche effect and changes in temporal evolution of strong wind fields, what may increase the hazard of extreme storms and MCF events, such as the case of 1872 or 2023 in the western part of the Baltic Sea.

On the contrary, studies of probabilities of extreme storm surges along the southern and eastern Baltic coast (Jensen, 2009; Jensen et al., 2009; Mäll et al., 2020) indicate increased hazard of storm-induced MCF events, in particular in the areas not covered with the sea-ice anymore (HECOM, 2021). This risk will increase due to combined effect of sea-level change and changes in circulation pattern. The research shows that along with the rising mean sea-level merely small changes in strength and direction of wind will cause a transition from high to extremely high surge levels and will influence the frequency and intensity of storm-induced coastal flooding in particular the eastern part of the Baltic Sea, along the coast of Gulf of Riga and Gulf of Finland (Weisse et al., 2021).

The research on socioeconomic effects of intensified storms and MCF events is limited and the most accurate predictions are being undertaken for the southern and eastern Baltic sea coastline. Paprotny and Terfenko (2017) have shown, using high-resolution LIDAR-based elevation, that in the case of the coastline along the southern Baltic Sea, the potential damage caused by increasing frequency of storms and associated MCF events would not exceed 0.005 % of national GDP until the last decade of the century, and only under the most extreme emission scenario. However, the protection provided by natural coastal barriers is at risk, as shoreline retreat could accelerate under sea-level rise (Vousdoukas et al., 2020b). This could further lead to loss of valuable coastal ecosystem services, to the tune of more than 1 % of regional GDP in many parts of the Baltic Sea (Paprotny et al., 2021). Still, the studies expect the erosion hazard and its impacts to be lower than in most parts of Europe or globally.

On the contrary in the northern part of the Baltic Sea, the climate change-induced sea-level increase will still be compensated by the glacial isostatic adjustment and the coastal hazard associated with storm-induced MCF will not increase significantly (Paprotny et al., 2019; Pellikka et al., 2018). Consequently, the northern Baltic Sea region has lower potential impacts and lower adaptation needs than most other parts of Europe (Vousdoukas et al., 2018, 2020a).

8. Directions for future research

Despite the fact of longstanding tradition of research on MCF events of various origin there still exist gaps in the understanding of how the sedimentary record of MCF relates to storm archives. It is not well

understood what are the characteristics of sites, where evidence is archived and why sedimentary evidence is patchy and discontinuous, even at sites where all environmental conditions favor marine inundations and preservation of inundation deposits. It is also not clear how MCF relate to enhanced storminess periods, and not all severe storm events cause coastal flooding.

Compiling a comprehensive database of storm references from historical sources within the Baltic is a task that remains to be undertaken in future source queries. In particular, due to the multiplicity of sources recording storms in 19th century is a challenging task. Currently, it is feasible to compile comprehensive references spanning the medieval period up to approximately 1500. In contrast, for the modern era, we possess knowledge about the most extreme storms, yet information regarding other storms is undoubtedly an ongoing process that will be continually augmented.

When considering the research on storms, their frequency and intensity based on the most recent history of instrumental measurements there is a vast amount of meteorological and hydrological data produced every day. However, the effective data exchange is hampered due to lack of well-designed sharing platforms, such as i.e. ecudo.pl/ and variable frequencies, methodologies of the data collection and storage. Effective transfer of data between various research centers will aid the unification of collection processes.

Further efforts are made to improve methodological advances in studying geological material or environments subjected to MCF. Techniques like mCT (computational microtomography), microXRF (micro X-ray fluorescence), or HSI (hyperspectral imaging) may be applied to achieve a more detailed, deep view of the sediment structures and answer some of the above questions. More studies should be carried out on the sedimentary records of recent storms with the known conditions of hydrology, meteorology, coastal geometry, etc., so that to better decipher the past storm events from sedimentary records. On-site monitoring using high-resolution remote sensing techniques may help in understanding fine sediment dynamics patterns and documenting the scale and impact of recent MCF events on the coastal environments. Special attention should be paid to the integration of data from different sensors and the development of new analytical methods aiming to reduce the cost and time of computation.

9. Conclusions

- The research on the past, contemporary and future storms and storm-induced MCF is undertaken by means of combination of sedimentary archives, historical sources and instrumental record including predictions based on numerical modelling. The data based on these three sources of information feeds the models, which then can be tested by means of sedimentary and geomorphological investigation of evidence along the coast or confrontation with historical sources.
- The longest timespan is encompassed by sedimentary archives and available for investigation by a combination of sedimentological methods, geochemistry, micropalaeontology, geophysics, which help identifying storm-induced MCF. However, the evidence for past coastal flooding in the form of sedimentary archives is limited and discontinuous, even at sites, that are selected to be prone to weather-induced marine inundations. The evidence for storm flooding documented around the Baltic Sea area comes primarily from the southern retrograding coast of the Baltic Sea.
- Study of historical sources gives an insight into storms and MCF events in areas occupied by humans and the time-spans of their socio-economic activity within the Baltic Sea coast comprising the past 800 years. They overlap in timespan with both sedimentological archives and instrumental record, however they give insight into the social context and influence of these phenomena on society.
- Instrumental records, spanning the last 200 years have the advantage of continuity; however they vary in temporal and spatial resolution. The major limitation is the change in geographical coverage with

time, which restricts comparability of the observations from various times in the history of measurements. The instrumental data is, however, a suitable source for numerical models and predictions, though it lacks low frequency, extreme events, which are the analogues for the worst case scenarios.

- The long-term storm frequency and intensity (storminess) has been obtained based on sedimentary archives, namely aeolian mineral input and geochemical signal in wetlands. The research was undertaken mainly on peatlands of the Scandinavian Peninsula and Jutland. 27 storminess phases have been identified (Björck and Clemmensen, 2004), confirmed later by Goslin et al. (2018).
- The longest and at the same time one of only a few, sedimentary records of storm-induced MCF have been discovered at the southern Baltic Sea coast (Mechelinki, Leszczyńska et al., 2022) in the form of multiple sand layers and geochemical signature (Uściniowicz, Sz., et al., 2020). It is not however clear, how these storm-induced coastal flooding events relate to enhanced storminess periods.
- The storm events influence the shaping of the coast by enhancing either erosion or accumulation. The major limitation for the interpretation of the sedimentary archives is the subsequent post-depositional changes of the deposits as well as subsequent erosion, both of the deposits as well as geomorphic forms associated with storms and MCF. The subsequent erosion of depositional evidence leads to the amalgamation of the evidence for multiple discrete events.
- The compilation of all three lines of evidence, namely sedimentary and historical archives as well as instrumental record, allow more detailed understanding of evolution and mechanisms of past storms and storm-induced MCF and following from that more accurate modelling of future phenomena.
- The general trend of rising sea-level and climatic changes, in particular strengthening of westerly circulation and deepening of low pressure centres, will increase the susceptibility of the coast to storm-induced flooding in the isostatically subsiding or slowly uplifting southern and eastern Baltic region in the future. The northern part of the Baltic Sea with prograding coast will not face an increased hazard associated with storm-induced coastal flooding.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by: the National Science Centre, Poland, grant OPUS no. 2018/29/B/ST10/00042 (Karl Statterger); the Excellence Initiative - Research University (IDUB) Adam Mickiewicz University grant no. 166/08/POB1/0013 (Karolina Leszczyńska); the Swedish Radiation Safety Authority project SSM2024-13975 (Helena Alexanderson); the Regional Excellence Initiative programme for 2024-2027, no. RID/SP/0045/2024/01 (Andrzej Giza, Dominik Paprotny, Pawł Terefenko., Tomasz Wolski); the National Science Centre, Poland, grant SONATA no. 2021/43/D/ST10/00185 (Damian Moskalewicz); the National Science Centre, Poland, grant OPUS no. 2020/37/B/ST10/00710 (Piotr Oliński); the Estonian Research Council grant PRG1471 (Alar Rosentau); the Swedish Reserch Council FORMAS, grant no. 2018-01784 (Anna Rutgersson). We are grateful to Anonymous Reviewers and the Editor for their comments, which help to improve the submitted manuscript. We also thank to our Colleagues who supported us during the writing of the manuscript with the discussion: Professor Jan Harff, Professor Kristaps Lampsters, Professor Mikel Fruergaard and Doctor Havu Pellikka.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2025.105137>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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